

Herbivore-Plant-Soil Feedbacks: Their Role on Plant Resource Partitioning and the Organization and Functioning of a Grazing Ecosystem

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Declaration

I herewith declare that this work has been originally produced by myself without having other external assistance than that specified in the chapters of the document. This work has not previously been presented in order to obtain a similar degree in any form.

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Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to investigate how different land management practices, including grazing by large herbivores and herbivores exclusion, affect belowground biological properties related to soil nutrient and carbon (C) cycling in nutrient-poor soils of British upland semi-natural grassland and moorland. A field (Chapter 2) and microcosm experiments (Chapter 3) were carried out to test how defoliation and grazing by herbivores affect key soil properties and ecosystem services through their effects on plant functional traits and the composition of the vegetation, respectively. Furthermore, indirect effects of herbivores (through their effect on soil properties) on competition of dominant upland graminoid were assessed (Chapter 4), including those related to plant competition for different chemical forms of nitrogen (N) (Chapter 5). Seasonal comparisons between acidic nutrient-poor grasslands grazed by large herbivores and herbivore-excluded areas (re-wilding) showed that grazing had similar effects to those observed in the microcosms experiment, increasing N mineralization rates and soil microbial activity. Such differences in soil properties between grazed and re-wilding areas were related to changes in plant functional groups, with re-wilding increasing the abundance of dwarf-shrubs which are known to slow-down nutrient cycling. Additionally, it was found that defoliation had consistent effects on soil properties,

decreasing soil microbial biomass C, and increasing soil N availability and rates of N mineralization. These general effects of defoliation on soil properties were independent of how different grass species varying in life-history traits responded to defoliation, suggesting that traits in this functional group (graminoids) are of less importance to mediate the effects of defoliation on soil properties in the nutrient-poor soils utilised.

On the other hand, differences in soil properties driven by contrasting grazing management affected plant competition between *Eriophorum vaginatum* (abundant in long-term ungrazed areas) and *Nardus stricta* (dominant in long-term grazed areas), so that the latter increased its negative effects on the former when grown in the soil coming from the grazed grassland. In contrast, the competitive effect of *E. vaginatum* on *N. stricta* was reduced in the grazed soils. This suggests the existence of a herbivore-plant-soil feedback mediated by soil microbes affecting plant competition. It was found that indirect effects of grazing on plant competition in these species were not explained by how different soil microbial communities affected competition for different forms of N (including dissolved inorganic N and dissolved organic N), but rather for the competitive traits of the superior competitor and the stimulating effects of grazing on N cycling. Overall, results of this work show the importance of herbivores in driving soil process through their effects on plant composition and soil microbes. More research is necessary to evaluate whether effects of grazing on nutrient cycling can have negative effects on other ecosystem services such as soil C sequestration. Effects of grazing on soil properties can, in turn, affect competition of plant species, which

showed differential abundances along gradients of grazing and soil physical properties. Whereas the effect of herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks on this plant species coexistence might be less important than direct effects of herbivores, my results suggest possible mechanisms by which plant species coexist in these poor-nutrient ecosystems.

To Greta and Martha.

“Believe those who are seeking the truth. Doubt those who found it” André
Gide.

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Chapter 1

General Introduction

1. General Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Ungulate herbivores are almost ubiquitous in terrestrial ecosystems where they have a key role in regulating vegetation dynamics and ecosystem functioning (McNaughton, 1985, 1986; Milchunas et al., 1988; McNaughton et al., 1988; Milchunas and Lauenroth, 1993; Bardgett and Wardle, 2003, 2010). The livestock production systems based on domestic relatives of these animals constitute an important industry, both in terms of its economic and environmental impacts worldwide (Fig.1.1). The global livestock population is estimated to be almost 2.5 billion head (only cattle and sheep, GLIPHA, 2011), with an increasing trend globally. In relation to this increasing trend in livestock numbers, Delgado et al. (2000) reported that from the 1970's to the middle of the 1990's, the consumption of livestock-related products in developing countries increased by 175 million metric tons, and the market value of such an increase was 155 billion dollars (1990 US dollars). Economic growth has been recognised as one of the main causes for the increased livestock numbers and the consequent higher inclusion of livestock products into people diets in a number of emergent economies (Smil, 2000). In many areas of the world, such increasing trends of consumption of livestock products translate into an incentive to increase livestock numbers or intensify production, thereby placing a great pressure on ecosystems and the services that they provide. Just to cite an example, livestock production was considered the main anthropogenic source of methane in the middle 1990's, showing an increasing trend (Stern and Kaufmann, 1996).

Figure 1.1: Grazing density worldwide as modelled between the relationship of herds size and environmental variables. Taken from FAO (2011a) -

Whereas much of this production is carried out under intensive farming conditions, a non-negligible proportion of world livestock production is carried out under extensive, nomadic or less intensified regimes (Delgado, 1999). Extensive grazing regimes usually take place in low productivity ecosystems such as in the high mountains and grasslands of the world, including those of upland temperate regions of the United Kingdom (Fig. 1.2). The study of factors affecting these areas is important since such ecosystems are highly vulnerable to disturbances (Holden et al., 2007), yet they have a high conservation value given the assemblage of species and ecosystem services provided by them, such as regulation of water quality and soil carbon (C) storage (Holden, 2009; Worrall and Evans, 2009). Therefore, the aim of this thesis is to examine direct and indirect effects of grazing by domestic herbivores on ecosystem functioning and structure in semi-natural mountain grasslands in the United Kingdom. Given the contemporary interests in linking above-ground processes (Wardle et al., 2004; van der Putten et al., 2009; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010), I focus on direct effects of herbivores on soil properties and processes, and indirect effects via interactions between key plant species and soil using a model upland ecosystem where contrasting grazing management has taken place.

In the next subsections of this introduction, I offer background material related to the main research topics covered in this thesis. First, I describe the main mechanisms by which large ungulate herbivores affect soil properties and processes and how, by doing so, herbivores can potentially affect plant-plant interactions through the operation of herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks. Then, I consider dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) as an N source for plant nutrition and its potential role in regulating plant-plant interactions in grazed grassland. I also outline the semi-natural mountain ecosystems which most

Figure 1.2: Grazing production systems in the world. The system is based on FAO and the International Livestock Research Institute classification. LGT in the legend corresponds to production systems in tropical and temperate highlands and uplands as those found through the United Kingdom uplands. Taken from FAO (2011b) -

of my research used as a model, and some of the drivers of environmental change these ecosystems face. Finally, I set the aims and objectives of the research, offering a brief description about the organization of this thesis and describing how the objectives and research questions address gaps in our understanding.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 Herbivore-mediated changes on ecosystem functioning: The above-belowground perspective

It was common practice in the grazing management literature to assess direct effects of herbivores on vegetation as a surrogate for its impacts on ecosystem-scale properties. For instance, early schemes aimed at assessing the effects of livestock on rangeland ecosystems based only on the response of different plant groups gained wide acceptance (Dyksterhuis, 1949). However, more recent approaches highlight the importance of an holistic perspective to take into account grazing effects on other ecosystem properties (Task Group on Unity in Concepts and Terminology, 1995). As an example of a more holistic view, research about grazing effects on plant-soil systems occupies an important place in the literature (Ritchie et al., 1998; Bardgett et al., 1998; Frank et al., 2000; Bardgett and Wardle, 2003; Mikola et al., 2009; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010; Frank et al., 2011).

It was Bardgett et al. (1998) and, more generally, Bardgett and Wardle (2003) who proposed that herbivore driven changes in vegetation could be coupled to changes in structure and functioning of soil microbial communities as well. They proposed that herbivores could affect soil microbial communities both directly, through inputs of ani-

1.2 Background

mal by-products and via physical disturbance, and indirectly by changing plant species composition (and concomitant changes in productivity and the quality and quantity of plant residues and root exudates entering into the soil food web). On the other hand, grazing-induced changes on soil microbial communities could, in turn, affect rates of soil nutrient cycling, which could feedback to the plant community (Fig. 1.3).

Figure 1.3: Hypothetical scenarios where ungulate herbivores stimulate (left) or decrease (right) soil nutrient cycling through their effects on composition of the vegetation (functional traits expressed under herbivory) and on soil microbial communities. Taken from Bardgett and Wardle (2003). -

One important aspect in the (Bardgett and Wardle, 2003) model is that it proposes that effect of herbivores on soil microbial communities and nutrient cycling depend on the plant functional traits promoted by herbivory. In this way, if herbivores increase the dominance of plants traits related, for instance, to low relative growth rates (RGR) and

low nitrogen (N) in tissues, then herbivores are expected to slow down soil nutrient cycling. Slowing-down in nutrient cycling is expected as a result of reductions in microbial activity and a shift to dominance by slow-growing soil organisms caused by plant residues with lower quality entering into the decomposer soil food web. These slow-growing soil organisms (mainly saprophytic fungi) would be characterised by a higher C to N ratio in microbial biomass and C assimilation efficiencies which would affect negatively nutrient cycling - the belowground side of the story. On the other hand, if herbivores promote plant traits such as high RGR, high N in tissues, then herbivory is expected to speed up rates of soil nutrient cycling as a result of higher soil microbial activity and a shift to fast-growing microbes (mainly bacteria).

(Bardgett and Wardle, 2003) model to explain herbivore-plant-soil interactions is partially - the aboveground side of the story - based on schemes suggesting covariation in plant traits across environmental gradients (Grime, 1977; Taylor et al., 1990; Westoby, 1998). It is thought that this covariation in plant traits are related to evolutionary trade-offs imposed on plant fitness across environmental gradients (Reich et al., 2003), including gradients related to grazing intensity (Briske, 1996; Díaz et al., 2001, 2007). Thus, different sets of plant traits represent contrasting approaches (e.g., in terms of resource allocation) to optimise fitness under grazing environments (Briske, 1996; Strauss and Agrawal, 1999; Tiffin, 2000; Leimu and Koricheva, 2006). Such different sets of plant traits (strategies) are broadly divided as those conferring either tolerance or avoidance to grazing (Briske, 1996; Tiffin, 2000). Tolerance comprises the set of physiological and morphological responses that promote plant growth under defoliation damage (e.g., compensatory photosynthesis and growth following defoliation; Strauss and Agrawal, 1999; Simms, 2000). On the other hand, avoidance is related to plant traits that reduce

biomass consumption by herbivores (e.g., chemical or morphological defences, traits that promote spatio-temporal protection from grazing; Briske, 1996; Rebollo et al., 2002).

It is unlikely that grazing tolerance and avoidance represent mutually exclusive responses by which plants cope with herbivory (Leimu and Koricheva, 2006; Núñez-Farfán et al., 2007). However, the concept has utility as grazing resistance traits can be related to other plant traits known to influence ecosystem processes, such as plant productivity, decomposition and plant competition (Wardle et al., 2002). In this line of reasoning, since plant species with contrasting growth traits occur on opposite ends of productivity gradients (Grime and Hunt, 1975; Grime, 2001) and grazing strategies expression seems to be dependent on productivity as well (Hamilton III et al., 1998), then effects of grazing on soil microbes and soil processes might depend on ecosystem productivity. Consequently, it has been proposed that stimulating effects of grazing on soil nutrient cycling might occur in high productivity ecosystems which high frequency of plants expressing grazing tolerance, whereas the opposite effect (depressing) should occur in low productivity systems where grazing avoidance is the norm (Bardgett and Wardle, 2010).

Other possibilities to that described above have been put forward. For instance, in an analysis of a mathematical model, (de Mazancourt et al., 1998) concluded that herbivores are likely to stimulate soil nutrient cycling if the nutrient losses associated with them are lower than other losses in the ecosystem scale, and they contribute with nutrient inputs beyond a certain threshold. Thus, it is important to test the generality of herbivore effects on soil properties both across wide gradients of plant functional traits and in ecosystems with low productivity, such as semi-natural mountain grasslands.

1.2.2 Herbivore-plant soil systems: Feedback on the plant community and plant species coexistence

The importance of plant-soil feedbacks for vegetation dynamics is now widely recognised (van der Putten, 2005; Bonanomi et al., 2005; Bezemer et al., 2006; Casper et al., 2008; Harrison and Bardgett, 2010). However, how such feedbacks are mediated by other biotic factors such as herbivory is less explored. Indirect effects of herbivory on plant performance via its effects on soil have been long recognised (Owen, 1980; Owen and Wiegert, 1981), but Bardgett and Wardle (2003) conceptual model recognises explicitly that it is through changes in soil microbial communities and soil processes that herbivore effects can feedback to the plant community (Fig. 1.3). This idea has been gaining strength, as it has been increasingly recognized that grazing can exert indirect effects on plant performance via its effect on soil properties and soil microbial communities (Ruess and McNaughton, 1987; Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Frank et al., 2003; Hamilton III et al., 2008; Sørensen et al., 2008a). An important implication of such feedback dynamics on plant performance is that they can potentially modify plant-plant interactions and therefore plant species coexistence.

A plant-soil feedback can be defined as the effect that certain soil microbial community influences on the performance of the plant species with which such microbes have previously grown (van der Putten, 2005). If the soil microbial community conditioned by a plant species has a positive effect on this plant growth, performance or fitness, then this effect is called a positive feedback. On the other hand, If the soil microbial community conditioned by a plant species has a negative effect on this plant growth, performance or fitness, then this effect is called a negative feedback.

The approach to test plant-soil feedbacks is conceptually similar to that in Koch's

postulates: i.e., soil microbial communities should differ between grown plant species or plant communities after a conditioning time; the effect of such differentiated soil microbial communities should be tested on the target plant species (van der Putten, 2005). However, Bever et al. (1997) and Bever (2003) showed that, in a pairwise plant species context, plant-soil feedbacks can be tested only by comparing the effects that soils pre-conditioned by both plant species have on the performance of each plant component in the pair (the “home vs away” approach, Fig. 1.4). Thus, by using this feedback approach, together with a plant competition model similar to the Lotka-Volterra approach, Bever (2003) concluded that plant-soil feedbacks may be important regulators of plant species coexistence through the modulation of the intensity of competitive interactions. For instance, the operation of a positive plant-soil feedback which increases the performance of a strong competitor could drive a weak competitor into local extinction much faster. However, as already discussed, it is less clear that such plant-soil feedbacks modifying plant species coexistence can be mediated by other ecological agents such as herbivores and the mechanisms by which such modifications could take place.

1.2.3 Dissolved organic nitrogen: Their role in low productivity habitats, plant nutrition and plant species coexistence

Dissolved organic N is a N pool made up of a diverse range of compounds including low molecular weight compounds (amino acids, amino sugars), and other heavier molecules including peptides and small proteins (Jones et al., 2005). What unifies all these compounds is the fact that they are associated to a carbon structure and that they are extracted from soil with water or mild salt solutions at room temperature (Jones et al., 2005; Jones and Willett, 2006). The size of the DON pool in soil solution is determined

Figure 1.4: Diagrammatic illustration of plant soil feedbacks. A plant species A conditions the soil where it grows (S_A). In turn, S_A soil affects the performance of A (α_A) and another plant species B (α_B). The same for plant species B, the soil it conditions (S_B), and the effect of S_B on A (β_A) and B (β_B). Depending on the effects of each soil on each plant species, species competition (C_A, C_B) and competitive exclusion can be intensified or reduced. Taken from Bever (2003).

by the balance between processes of consumption and production (Kalbitz et al., 2000; Chen and Xu, 2006, Fig. 1.5). Main production processes include: 1) decomposition of soil organic matter, plant residues and rhizodeposits carried out by soil microorganisms (Schimel and Weintraub, 2003; Schimel and Bennett, 2004); 2) microbial biomass turnover (Schimel and Weintraub, 2003; Chen and Xu, 2006); and 3) direct deposition (through wet deposition or throughfall, Chen and Xu, 2006). On the other hand, the main consumption processes are 1) direct uptake by microbes (including mycorrhizae) and plants (Barraclough, 1997; Schimel and Bennett, 2004); 2) ecosystem loss through leaching (Harriman et al., 1998; Cleveland et al., 2004); and 3) stabilization with organic matter or the soil mineral phase through a number of physicochemical processes (Jones and Hodge, 1999).

Since factors regulating DON production-consumption processes vary hugely across environmental gradients, one would expect to find differences in the size of this N pool among different ecosystem types. Among these differences, it has been suggested that low productivity ecosystems should have a greater proportion of this N pool relative to DIN (Christou et al., 2005; Farrell et al., 2011), perhaps as a result of conditions limiting microbial activity and N mineralization (Schimel and Bennett, 2004, but see Jones and Hodge 1999; O'Dowd et al. 1999; Jones and Kielland 2002).

Evidence showing that terrestrial plants can directly take up several DON forms is accumulating (for a detailed list of studies see Lipson and Näsholm, 2001; Weigelt et al., 2005; Näsholm et al., 2009b). Not only can plants take up simple DON forms of low molecular weight (e.g., amino acids, amides, polypeptides), it has been shown that plants can satisfy their N requirements exclusively from complex organic N sources (proteins)

Figure 1.5: Diagram showing main steps involved in dissolved organic N (SON in the figure) cycling in a forest ecosystem. a = decomposition, b = cell uptake, c = microbial release, d = microbial biomass turnover, e = root uptake, f = root exudation, g = humification, h = leaching, i = microbial predation. SIN = soil inorganic N. Taken from Chen and Xu (2006) -

without the assistance of microbial symbionts (Paungfoo-Lonhienne et al., 2008). Such evidence has made it clear that previous assumptions about how plants rely completely on release of dissolved inorganic N (DIN) - through N mineralization or microbial biomass turnover - (Schimel and Bennett, 2004) might not be valid.

Utilization of DON by plants might have important ecological implications. In this way, it has been shown that plants differ in their preferences of different chemical forms of N (McKane et al., 2002; Harrison et al., 2007, 2008). For example, McKane et al. (2002) showed that the graminoid *Eriophorum vaginatum* utilized glycine and NH_4^+ , which were the most abundant N forms, whereas the subordinate species *Carex bigelowii* preferred the least available form, namely NO_3^- , in a tundra ecosystem in Alaska. This example, as with many others (e.g., Lipson et al., 1999; Bardgett et al., 2003), suggests that differential uptake of N chemical forms among plant species could be a mechanism regulating plant coexistence and plant-soil microbial interactions. Since different microbial communities can differ in their effects on a number of soil processes (Bardgett et al., 1996; Strickland et al., 2009), factors affecting microbial communities could affect plant species N uptake preferences, which is an aspect of plant-soil feedbacks still poorly explored (Ashton et al., 2008).

1.2.4 Extensive grazing systems: Semi-natural mountain grasslands and the United Kingdom study case

The Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary (CD, 2011) defines upland as: "area of land that is situated high up, such as on a hill or mountain". However, for environmental management purposes, the United Kingdom department of rural affairs (DEFRA, 2011b) equates the concept of upland with that of Less Favoured Areas as: "land which is

suitable for extensive livestock production but not, owing to the geography of the area, other agricultural production” (compare Figs. 1.2 1.6). In this thesis, I use the terms upland, semi-natural mountain grassland, and moorland interchangeably.

In the United Kingdom, grazing as a management activity in the uplands has long historical roots (Simmons, 2003). However, post-war land use policies provided incentives for farmers to increase livestock numbers in upland habitats over the last part of the twentieth century (Simmons, 2003). For instance, trends of sheep numbers in the UK showed dramatic increases since the 1950s until 1990’s when herd sizes stabilised or decreased slightly (Fuller and Gough, 1999). This increase in sheep numbers has been put forward as one the main drivers of a large scale change from dwarf-shrub dominated moors into acidic grasslands across the British uplands (Bardgett et al., 1995). Direct effects of herbivores on vegetation composition in upland habitats are relatively well studied. Thus, it is thought that the mentioned replacement of moorland vegetation by grasses is driven by direct grazing effects on the competitive balance among plant species (Welch, 1984, 1986; Hartley and Amos, 1999; Hartley and Mitchell, 2005), although other environmental factors, such as soil moisture content and organic layer depth, might be involved (Ratcliffe, 1959; Edgell, 1971; Rodwell, 1992; Genney et al., 2002). A consequence of herbivory is that plant species of low palatability to domestic herbivores, such as *Nardus stricta*, might have a high invasibility and persistence over a large part of upland ecosystems as a result of the negative effects of herbivory on their competitors (Fenton, 1937; Rawes, 1961; Welch, 1986). Indirect effects of herbivores (those caused by herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks) can also influence the organization of upland habitats, but are far less understood and studied.

* The uplands are contained within the Less Favoured Areas (LFAs) boundaries. LFAs were established in 1975 as a means to provide support to mountainous and hill farming areas but were later widened to include other disadvantaged areas.

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Figure 1.6: Geographical distribution of uplands in England. Taken from DEFRA (2011a).

The recent introduction of the reform in the common agricultural policy within the European Union would certainly have a large effect on the way upland areas are managed (Condliffe, 2009). As this reform decouples subsidy payments from production, there might be an incentive for certain farmers to supply other ecosystem services (Oglethorpe, 2005), such as those related to soil C sequestration and the maintenance of supporting services such as soil nutrient cycling. This might imply reductions in livestock population in upland areas with concomitant changes in the structure and composition of the vegetation (referred as to re-wilding). Estimating the effects of re-wilding on ecosystem processes is therefore important to determine trade-offs in different ecosystem services related to different land use management options.

1.2.5 Background summary

In summary, the impact of herbivores on plant community composition and functional traits can affect soil microbial communities and nutrient cycling. However, whether these changes occur across a range of plant functional traits is still unclear (Chapter 3). Secondly, contrasting effects of herbivores on soil nutrient cycling and soil microbial communities are expected in ecosystems with contrasting productivity, although more information is necessary on this subject. Thus, it is important to test the effects of herbivores on soil properties in low productivity ecosystems such as those found in the British uplands (Chapter 2). Furthermore, since changes in grazing management policies are expected in these ecosystems, it is also important to evaluate how grazing management can affect ecosystem services in these habitats (Chapter 2). Thirdly, plant soil feedbacks are key mechanisms in the organization of vegetation through their effects on

1.3 Thesis layout: Aims and hypotheses

plant species performance and plant-plant competitive interactions. However, whether plant-soil feedbacks can be caused by effects of herbivores on soil microbial communities and soil processes is poorly understood (Chapter 4). Finally, plants are able to take up different chemical forms of N, and plant species can differ in their preferences for DON or DIN. These plant species N preferences could have consequences for plant species coexistence and competition. However, if herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks are able to alter plant competition through N uptake preferences has been rarely addressed (Chapter 6).

Next, the aims and hypotheses of this research are presented together with the organization of the chapters.

1.3 Thesis layout: Aims and hypotheses

As stated above, this thesis aims to test effects of herbivores on soil properties and plant-plant interactions in model upland ecosystem in northern England, where contrasting grazing management has taken place. To address this aim, a series of specific objectives were tested through a combination of field and glasshouse studies, as detailed below.

- 1) To determine the effects of different grazing management on soil properties in poor-nutrient semi-mountain ecosystems in northern England.
- 2) To determine the effects of defoliation on soil properties across a range of temperate grass species differing in functional traits.
- 3) To assess how the effects of grazing on soil properties (herbivore-plant-soil feedback) affect competition dynamics in *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*.
- 4) To link herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks effects on plant competition to effects of

1.3 Thesis layout: Aims and hypotheses

soil microbes on N uptake preferences of *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*.

Chapter 2 aimed to determine, in the field, the effects of grazing on soil properties and ecosystem services related to C and N cycling in semi-natural mountain grasslands in northern England. Since herbivores promote plant functional groups with traits related to higher litter quality than those occurring in ungrazed areas, it was hypothesised that grazing would cause higher rates of nutrient cycling. Soil biological properties between a continuously sheep-grazed acidic grassland dominated by *N. stricta*, *Festuca spp.*, and *Agrostis capillaris*, and a 10-year fenced-off area (re-wilding) were contrasted, taking into account seasonal variability. It was observed that re-wilding changed the composition of functional plant groups, as well as pools of plant biomass. Herbivores promoted nutrient cycling, microbial activity and reduced the proportion of DON:DIN in comparison to re-wilding conditions, suggesting that grazing is associated with faster nutrient cycling. Despite these results, no differences in total soil C or N storage were detected between different grazing managements, suggesting that low levels of sheep grazing are compatible with soil C storage.

Chapter 3 aims to determine the effects of defoliation on soil properties across a range of temperate grass species differing in functional traits. In this chapter, a number of grass species from a range of life-story and trait strategies were subjected to different levels of defoliation to evaluate soil responses to plant defoliation. It was hypothesised that soil responses would mirror plant species responses. Defoliation caused consistent effects on all plant species reducing plant performance overall. Despite the wide range of life-history traits included, only subtle intra-specific responses to defoliation were observed, but they indicated differences in defoliation resistance among plant species.

1.3 Thesis layout: Aims and hypotheses

Defoliation caused consistent effects on soil properties as well, such as decrease in soil microbial biomass C and increases in N availability. Again, despite the broad range of life history used, no consistent effects of defoliation were observed through its effects on plant species. It is concluded that, under certain circumstances such as poor nutrient soils, defoliation is an important mechanisms affecting soil properties, but independently from plant species identity to a large extent.

Chapter 4 assessed how grazing effects on soil properties affect competition balance between *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*, two graminoids with contrasting abundances along grazing and soil properties gradients in semi-natural mountain grasslands. Based on differences on soil properties between grazed and re-wilding areas previously observed, it was hypothesised that species would perform better on the soils where they are dominant. Then, a microcosm experiment was set-up to test effects of grazing-induced plant-soil feedbacks on intra- and inter-specific competition in these plant species. It was observed that soil from the grazed area increased intra-specific competition in both plant species, since this soil showed higher microbial activity and N mineralization rates. However, when it came to inter-specific competition, the grazed-conditioned soil increased the negative effect that the plant species dominating the grazed area (*N. stricta*) had on *E. vaginatum*. Grazed-conditioned soil also reduced to a half the negative effect of *E. vaginatum* on *N. stricta*. These grazing-mediated plant-soil feedbacks effects on intra- and inter-specific competition had not been described yet, but they could contribute to the persistence of *N. stricta* in long-term grazed upland habitats and its invasibility in other terrestrial ecosystems.

Chapter 5 examined how competitive interactions between *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta* could be affected by herbivore-plant-soil feedback effects on plant N uptake pref-

1.3 Thesis layout: Aims and hypotheses

erences. Here, based on results about indirect effects of grazing on plant competition described above, it was hypothesised that observed changes in competitive outcome could be partially explained by effects of soil microbial communities on plant N preferences. A microcosm plant competition experiment was set-up using soil inoculum from grazed and re-wilding areas, and tracking the fate of DON and DIN compounds enriched with ^{15}N and ^{13}C stable isotopes into plant biomass. Unlike expectations, microbial communities did not have any effect of the way plant species competed for N chemical forms. However, plant species differed in their preference of N chemical forms, indicating perhaps main soil conditions of the habitats where they show contrasting abundances. *Nardus stricta*, the superior competitor in the pairwise interaction, affected the relative N preferences of *E. vaginatum*, but it was not affected by inter-specific competition suggesting that conditions under which these species coexist in upland habitats might not be related to mechanisms reducing niche overlap in N use.

Finally, in Chapter 6, I discuss my overall results and provide concluding remarks for the work.

Chapter 2

Influence of re-wilding practices versus sheep grazing on aboveground and belowground properties of upland grasslands

This chapter has been submitted to *Ecosystems, Agriculture and Environment*, authored and under the name of: “Medina-Roldán, E., J. Paz-Ferreiro, and R.D. Bardgett. Influence of re-wilding practices versus sheep grazing on aboveground and belowground properties of upland grasslands”. Co-author JPF contributed with logistical and field work, and RDB is the supervisor of the thesis work. Manuscript is currently under review. Superficial changes were done for the sake of the thesis format.

3. Influence of re-wilding practices versus sheep grazing on aboveground and belowground properties of upland grasslands

2.1 Abstract

Exclusion of domestic herbivores (re-wilding) is becoming an increasingly important conservation tool for the restoration of biodiversity in degraded habitats. We evaluated the impacts of re-wilding after 7 years on vegetation and belowground properties in a landscape-level, moorland re-wilding project in the Yorkshire Dales, northern England. Our aim was to test whether changes in vegetation and soil properties associated with re-wilding impacted positively on ecosystem services related to soil carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) cycling. We measured a number of vegetation and soil biological properties in replicate plots of re-wilded moorland, and compared them with those in an adjacent grazed grass-dominated moorland over a period of one year in order to capture seasonal variation in our selected variables. After 7 years, re-wilding significantly affected the composition of vegetation, increasing the proportion of dwarf-shrubs at the expense of graminoids. In turn, this caused significant changes in soil properties, increasing plant litter mass and soil moisture content, and reducing rates of ammonium mineralisation, soil microbial activity, and microbial biomass N. There was also a shift in the availability of soil N forms, with the ratio of dissolved organic to inorganic N increasing as a result of re-wilding. These changes brought about by re-wilding suggest a long-term slowing down

of rates of C and N cycling. However, as yet, this has had no detectable impact on total C and N stocks in surface soil, which might be expected in the longer term. Overall, our findings indicate that re-wilding has significant consequences for both vegetation and soil biological processes, which in the longer-term are likely to have an impact on ecosystem services of C and N sequestration.

2.2 Keywords

Moorland, grass-dominated ecosystems, carbon, nitrogen, soil properties, *Calluna vulgaris*, ecosystem services, uplands, grazing management

2.3 Introduction

There is growing interest in understanding the effects of different land use options on ecosystem functioning and the production of ecosystem goods and services, such as primary production, nutrient cycling and carbon (C) sequestration (Post and Kwon, 2000; Foley et al., 2005; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Despite their limited agricultural value, moorland ecosystems, which cover a large part of the British land-surface, have been dramatically shaped by a long history of land use (Roberts, 1959; Bardgett et al., 1995; Simmons, 2003). In particular, a long history of sheep grazing, and historic changes in the grazing pressure, has had well documented effects on the structure and functioning of these moorland ecosystems (Hunter, 1962; Brack, 1978; Anderson and Yalden, 1981; Bardgett et al., 2001; Done and Muir, 2001). One of the most dramatic effects of historic sheep grazing has been the replacement of dwarf- shrub moorland veg-

etation, dominated by *Calluna vulgaris* and other dwarf- shrubs of the Ericacea family, by acidic, low productivity grassland of a lower conservation value (Smith, 1918; Fenton, 1937; Bardgett et al., 1995; Thompson et al., 1995). This grazing-induced transition in vegetation has also had significant effects on belowground communities and the functioning of these ecosystems, with heavily grazed, grass-dominated ecosystems typically having faster rates of nutrient and C cycling than their less heavily grazed dwarf-shrub counterparts (Bardgett et al., 1997, 2001).

Over the last few decades, the restoration of heather dominated moorland from heavily grazed grassland has been a high conservation priority in the UK (Bardgett et al., 1995; Reed et al., 2009). This has largely been due to the high amenity value of heather moorland, its spatial extent in the United Kingdom, and the importance of this ecosystem as an habitat for several organisms such as for the feeding and/or breeding of many birds, including several rare species (Thompson et al., 1995) and groups of invertebrates (Hartley et al., 2003). More recently, interest in moorland ecosystems and their management has shifted in recognition of the broad range of ecosystem services that they provide, especially in terms of their role in climate regulation through acting as major stores of soil C (Garnett et al., 2000, 2001; Ward et al., 2007). Indeed, it is widely recognized that upland and moorland habitats represent one of the UKs largest stores of C (Milne and Brown, 1997), and, in some situations, widespread historic heavy grazing has led to declines in soil C contents of these ecosystems (Bardgett et al., 2001; Grayston et al., 2004). Thus, restoration projects aimed at reducing and/or excluding grazing to increase the abundance of heather and other dwarf-shrubs (commonly known as re-wilding) could have additional benefits for the functioning of these ecosystems and the services that they provide (Mitchell et al., 2008), and have therefore been given a

high priority in the United Kingdom (Pakeman et al., 2003; Littlewood et al., 2006; Mitchell et al., 2008).

Here, we tested for the effects that re-wilding on soil biological properties related to C and nitrogen (N) cycling using a 7-year, landscape scale re-wilding experiment located in the Ingleborough National Nature Reserve in the Yorkshire Dales, northern England. This landscape-scale experiment provided an opportunity to test how re-wilding schemes, which are increasingly widespread in the United Kingdom (Hartley and Mitchell, 2005; Mitchell et al., 2008), affect vegetation and a range of soil biological properties that underpin multiple ecosystem services delivery in these fragile habitats, especially those related to C and N sequestration. Specifically, we tested for re-wilding effects on vegetation biomass (aboveground and belowground) and composition, and soil properties, including the biomass and activity of microorganisms, rates of soil N mineralisation, the availability of soluble C and N forms, and total soil contents of C and N. Our sampling included seasonal measurements of most variables in order to determine how the effects of re-wilding on the above ecosystem properties varied across the year. We hypothesize that re-wilding and the concomitant change in the vegetation are associated with a slowing-down in N and C cycling, characterised by reductions in rates of N mineralisation and microbial activity, and an increase in soil C and N content.

2.4 Material and Methods

2.4.1 Site description and experimental design

The study area is located at Ingleborough National Nature Reserve (NNR) in the Yorkshire Dales National Park, northern England (54.18° N, 2.36° E; UK National Grid

2.4 Material and Methods

Reference Number SD 763762). The climate is temperate maritime, with a mean annual precipitation of 1840 mm (averaged for 10 years, UK Meteorological Office 2010, see Fig. 2.6b). Several vegetation types are located within the nature reserve, but large areas are covered by sheep-grazed, acidic grassland dominated by the graminoids *Nardus stricta* L., *Festuca ovina* L., *Agrostis capillaris* L. and *Eriophorum vaginatum* L. (Rodwell, 1992). Soils are derived from carboniferous sandstones in the Yoredale group (Waltham, 2008) with a pH of 4.5 (based on a triplicate measure in 1:2.5 soil to water suspensions w/v) and an organic surface horizon of 20-30 cm depth. This grassland type and its variants are widespread across western parts of upland Britain where it forms the mainstay vegetation type of the sheep farming industry (Rodwell, 1992).

Our study commenced in 2007, when we selected 2 adjacent areas of moorland of similar topography and altitude with contrasting recent grazing management (Fig. 2.1). One of them (hereafter the re-wilding area) is a 170 ha area which was previously grazed by sheep at stocking rates of 1-3 ewes ha^{-1} , but which was fenced off in 2000 to exclude livestock as part of a landscape-scale re-wilding experiment set-up to restore it into a heather dominated community (Colin Newlands, Natural England, *pers. comm.*). The second area (hereafter the grazed area) is an immediately adjacent 58 ha acidic grassland of similar topography and soils, which has had a very similar grazing history to the re-wilding area. However, since 1996 stocking rates have been maintained at 4 ewes ha^{-1} , with some cattle grazing for 10 weeks from since mid-July onwards. The winter grazing regime in this area includes a maximum stocking rate of 1.5 ewes ha^{-1} from early November until mid-March. As far as we are aware, neither area has received artificial fertilisers, manures or supplementary feeding.

Given that re-wilding was done at the landscape level, pseudo-replication was un-

avoidable in that similar areas were not available in the area. However, in order to minimize the sources of error associated with this problem, we used multiple, randomly located plots within the grazed and re-wilding areas. For this, 6 experimental plots, each 4 X 4 m, were randomly positioned along a NW-SE transect within each of the experimental areas. Individual sampling plots within the re-wilding and grazed areas were of similar topography with an average soil depth of 40 cm, and were representative of vegetation and soil conditions at the landscape-scale on both sites (Fig. 2.1). Once the experimental plots were established, each replicated experimental plot was split into 16 1 X 1 m sub-plots wherein all soil and vegetation samples were randomly taken.

2.4.2 Soil and vegetation sampling

We sampled soil and vegetation 5 times from mid spring 2007 until early summer 2008 in order to capture seasonal variability in responses of soil properties to re-wilding. On each sampling date, a turf that included vegetation and the organic peat horizon (20 X 20 cm area, 20 cm depth) was excavated from each experimental sub-plot on each replicated plot by using a shovel. Samples were kept immediately within coolers after sampled and transported back to the laboratory where they were then stored at 4 °C until the analytical procedures took place within 5 days after collection. Additionally, root biomass estimation was determined from two soil cores taken to a depth of 10 cm within the organic horizon on each sub-plot and sampling date. We inserted perforated PVC pipes (21 mm diameter X 1000 mm length) on each experimental plot in order to record the water table depth (Oechel et al., 1998) on approximately two-weekly intervals from mid July until mid November 2007.

2.4.3 Above- and belowground biomass, and size of litter horizons

Dry mass pools in the sampled turves were divided in 4 main components following Ward et al. (2007): 1) aboveground plant biomass; 2) a litter (L) horizon underlying the green vegetation but well differentiated from; 3) a horizon with unidentifiable vegetation residues and humified plant material (F and H horizon not recorded on the second sampling period); and 4) the organic horizon (O horizon). Aboveground plant biomass was sorted into plant functional groups (Ward et al., 2009), namely graminoids, dwarf-shrubs, forbs and a group of non-flowering plants which included mosses and species in the division Lycopodiophyta, i.e., *Lycopodium sp*, oven-dried at 70 °C for 48 hours, and weighed to determine standing crop biomass and plant growth form relative abundance. The L and F and H horizons were oven-dried, as described above, to estimate their dry biomass. Roots were recovered by washing and sieving (minimum mesh size 0.5 mm) soil cores, oven-dried and weighed to determine root biomass.

2.4.4 Soil analysis

Before the O horizon was perturbed, we took a core from the soil turves with a soil sampler (35 mm diameter, 100 mm depth) in order to measure bulk density and soil moisture content by standard procedures. The remaining soil in the turves was passed through a 2 mm sieve prior to laboratory analysis. Sieved soil from each sampling date was analysed in the laboratory for a number of biological properties that are described below. Measures of total soil C and N content for two different sampling dates were done in a Carlo Erba EA-1108 elemental analyser in SAI-UDC University of Coruña. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed that soil % C did not vary across sampling dates

($W = 71$, $n = 12$, $P = 0.97$); therefore, we calculated the total soil C and N for both management regimes assuming no change over the sampling period.

2.4.5 Soil N availability and dissolved organic C and N

Soil ammonium (NH_4^+) content was measured by extracting 10 g of fresh soil in 1 M KCl, stirring the extracts during 1 hour on an orbital shaker, filtering them in Whatman paper No.1, and determining NH_4^+ concentration by continuous-flow colorimetry using the sodium nitroprusside reaction in a Bran and Luebbe AutoAnalyzer 3. Nitrate (NO_3^-) was measured in the same way as NH_4^+ , but through the sulfanilamide method. Net NH_4^+ and NO_3^- mineralisation rates were estimated as the difference between non-incubated and incubated soil samples (Campbell and Rochefort, 2003). Ten g of fresh soil were incubated at 25 °C during 14 days after which they were extracted as described above. Non-incubated samples were extracted shortly after sampling. Ammonium and NO_3^- concentrations were measured colorimetrically as already described. Dissolved organic C (DOC) and N (DON) were measured by shaking 10 g of soil in 70 mL of distilled water during 10 minutes and filtering the soil-water extracts in Whatman paper No. 1. DOC was measured by the difference between total C and inorganic C in the soil-water extracts as analysed by a Shimadzu 5000A TOC analyser (Shimadzu Inc., Japan). DON was measured by continuous-flow colorimetry as the difference in the soil-water extracts between total N after digestion in potassium persulfate and inorganic N.

2.4.6 Microbial biomass and activity

Microbial biomass C and N were assayed by the chloroform fumigation extraction technique. Microbial biomass C was estimated according to Vance et al. (1987) by extracting 5 g of fresh soil in 0.5 M K_2SO_4 , shaking the soil-extract for 30 min in an orbital shaker, filtering the soil extract in Whatman paper No. 1. Microbial biomass C was calculated as the difference between fumigated and non-fumigated soils after analysing the extracts for C content as described for DOC using an extraction efficiency of 0.45 (Sparling et al., 1990). Microbial biomass N was assayed by digesting the soil extracts with potassium persulfate (Cabrera and Beare, 1993) and determining N contents with flow colorimetry as described above. Microbial biomass N was calculated as the N difference between fumigated and non-fumigated soils using an extraction efficiency of 0.54 (Brookes et al., 1985). Soil basal respiration was determined following Bardgett et al. (1999b) as the production of CO_2 by soils after a 24-h period of incubation at 25 °C of 1 g dry mass equivalent soil within sealed McCartney bottles. The CO_2 production after the incubation period was measured by injecting 1 mL of sample from the bottles' head-space into an ADC 225 MK3 IRGA (ADC Bioscientific Ltd., Hoddesdon, UK) and using respective blanks and CO_2 standards.

2.4.7 Statistical analysis

We tested for significant statistical effects of re-wilding on all dependent variables by using repeated measures ANOVA through the linear mixed models routine in R (Pinheiro et al., 2008). Land management (re-wilding vs grazing) and date of sampling (seasonal variation) were considered fixed effects (between and within-subjects factors

respectively). On the other hand, the experimental plots (subjects) within each sampling date were considered as the random factor. Differences in the time length intervals among sampling events were taken into account by specifying a linear correlation structure for the dates factor. Total soil C differences between land management regimes were tested with a t-test. For most variables we analysed factor effects on a per square meter basis using bulk density and a soil depth of 10 cm. All variables were transformed to satisfy normality criteria but results and figures are presented for untransformed variables using means \pm se. All analysis were carried out with the R package for Linux (R Development Core Team, 2010).

Given the high number of zeros in the plant functional groups dataset, the effect of re-wilding on the proportion of plant functional groups was tested by using a non-parametric multivariate ANOVA (Anderson, 2008) implemented in R (Oksanen et al., 2010). Land management (re-wilding vs grazing) and sampling date were used as the factors. If the overall model result was significant, the importance of each single plant functional group was estimated by removing one of the groups from the model and comparing the resultant pseudo- F and R -square values (a decrease in R -square and lack of significance were used as the criteria to decide whether certain plant functional group was important).

2.5 Results

2.5.1 Vegetation composition

Re-wilding resulted in significant changes in plant functional group abundances - abundance is expressed in terms of relative biomass - ($F_{1,48} = 8.0$, $P < 0.005$). When averaged across sampling dates, re-wilding caused a significant increase in the abundance of

Figure 2.1: The field site at Ingleborough National Nature Reserve, northern England, showing the main vegetation characteristics of a re-wilding area where domestic herbivores have been excluded over 7 years (G^0) and an adjacent grazed acidic grassland (G^+). Images obtained from <http://maps.google.com/> and authors' own collection -

dwarf-shrubs (20.4 ± 1.1 vs 2.9 ± 3.4 % in the re-wilding and grazed area, respectively, Fig. 2.2a) and a decrease in the proportion of graminoid species (23.0 ± 4.8 vs 43.0 ± 4.7 %), despite high between-plot variation in plant abundances. Mosses and other non-flowering plants (mainly *Lycopodium sp*) did not differ in abundance between the different management regimes, although they were an important component of the vegetation on both areas (52.0 ± 4.2 and 54.0 ± 5.2 % in the re-wilding and grazed areas, respectively, Fig. 2.2a). Seasonal differences in vegetation were of marginal significance ($F_{4,48} = 1.9$, $P = 0.08$), although across treatments there was a lower relative abundance of dwarf-shrubs in May 2007 and June 2008 (Fig. 2.2a), and of graminoids in July 2007 and January 2008.

2.5.2 Above- and belowground biomass, and size of litter horizons

There was a significant interaction between land management and season ($F_{4,38} = 14.6$, $P < 0.0001$) on aboveground biomass, as the higher values observed in the re-wilding area in May and July 2007 were not recorded in the following sampling dates (Fig. 2.3a). Root biomass was not affected by re-wilding ($F_{1,10} = 1.1$, $P = 0.32$), but it varied significantly with season across both sites ($F_{4,36} = 10.6$, $P < 0.0001$), being maximal in early summer (May 2007) and minimal in winter (January 2008) (4280 ± 570 vs 1710 ± 328 g DM m⁻² respectively, averaged across land management, Fig. 2.3c). Re-wilding increased the size of the litter (L) horizon (980 ± 124 vs 590 ± 67 g DM m⁻² in the re-wilding and grazed area, respectively, Fig. 2.3b), although this difference was only marginally significant ($F_{1,10} = 4.3$, $P = 0.06$). The size of the L horizon also varied seasonally across management treatments ($F_{4,38} = 15.5$, $P < 0.0001$), although this was mainly down to the lower dry mass recorded in July 2007 (Fig. 2.3b). The F and H

Figure 2.2: Effects of re-wilding (G^0) vs sheep grazing (G^+) across seasons on: a) plant functional groups abundance; b) total soil C content; c) total soil N content. Forb = non-legume herbaceous dicots; graminoids = plants in Poaceae and Cyperaceae (mainly *Eriophorum vaginatum*); shrubs = *Calluna vulgaris* and *Vaccinium myrtillus*; and nsper = mosses and other non-flowering plants. In a) horizontal axis (day/month/yr). In b) and c) data are mean \pm se, $n = 12$ -

2.5 Results

horizon was not affected by re-wilding ($F_{1,10} = 0.4$, $P > 0.50$), and it did not vary seasonally ($F_{3,30} = 2.2$, $P > 0.10$; pooled estimates across management and dates 2330 ± 171 g DM m^{-2} , Fig. 2.3d). Re-wilding did not affect total soil C, measured as both % C or C content (g C m^{-2}) ($t = 0.7$, $df = 17.9$, $P = 0.50$ and $t = 0.7$, $df = 20$, $P > 0.45$ respectively; Fig. 2.2b), or total soil N (neither N % nor N content $t = 0.4$, $df = 8.3$, $P > 0.60$ and $t = 0.2$, $df = 7.4$, $P > 0.80$; Fig. 2.2c).

Figure 2.3: Effects of re-wilding (G⁰) vs sheep grazing (G⁺) across seasons on: a) plant aboveground biomass; b) mass of the litter horizon; c) belowground biomass; d) F+H horizon. All data are mean \pm se, per data point $n = 6$. This dry mass pools division follows that in Ward et al. (2007). Horizontal axis (day/month/yr) -

2.5.3 Soil N availability and dissolved organic matter

There was a significant interaction between land management and season for potential net NH_4^+ mineralisation rate ($F_{4,38} = 4.1$, $P < 0.01$): rates of NH_4^+ mineralisation tended

to be greater in soil of the grazed than the re-wilding area across all sampling points in 2007, but this trend was reversed in late January 2008, but changed once again in June 2008 when NH_4^+ was larger in the grazed area (Fig. 2.4a). Despite the significant interaction term, the rate of NH_4^+ mineralisation was consistently greater during spring and summer sampling points of 2007 ($F_{4,39} = 6.0$, $P < 0.0001$). Potential net NO_3^- mineralisation rate was not affected by re-wilding ($F_{1,10} = 0.2$, $P > 0.50$), but this measure varied significantly with sampling date ($F_{4,39} = 6.2$, $P < 0.0001$), although this response was mainly due to the exceptionally high values recorded in May 2007 (Fig. 2.4b). As with NO_3^- mineralisation, soil concentrations of DOC ($F_{1,10} = 0.4$, $P = 0.5$) and DON ($F_{1,10} = 0.7$, $P = 0.4$) did not respond to re-wilding (Figs. Fig. 2.4c and 2.4d), although their concentrations differed with time of sampling (DOC, $F_{4,37} = 10.0$, $P < 0.0001$; DON, $F_{4,37} = 34.9$, $P < 0.0001$). In the case of DOC, this was due to a higher concentrations being detected in July 2007 in comparison to the other sampling points ($87.4 \pm 14.9 \text{ g C m}^{-2}$ versus $33.9 \pm 1.9 \text{ g C m}^{-2}$), whereas for DON, concentrations were significantly higher in July 2007 and June 2008 (6.9 ± 0.8 and $5.9 \pm 0.8 \text{ g N m}^{-2}$ respectively) than on the other dates (Fig. 2.4d). Re-wilding did not affect the DOC:DON ratio ($F_{1,10} = 1.8$, $P = 0.2$), which only varied across sampling dates ($F_{4,38} = 19.2$, $P < 0.0001$), mainly as a result of a significant difference between the January and June 2008 measurements (Fig. 2.4e). Re-wilding increased the ratio of soil DON to dissolved inorganic N (DIN) ($F_{1,10} = 7.7$, $P < 0.05$, Fig. 2.4f), which also varied seasonally but mainly as a result of the high value recorded in June 2008 ($F_{4,36} = 54.0$, $P < 0.0001$).

Figure 2.4: Effects of re-wilding (G^0) vs sheep grazing (G^+) across seasons on: a) net potential NH_4^+ ; b) net potential NO_3^- mineralisation rates; c) dissolved organic carbon (DOC); d) dissolved organic nitrogen (DON); e) DOC:DON ratio; and f) DON: dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN). All data are mean \pm se, per data point $n = 6$. Broken lines in a) and b) represent the point where mineralisation is zero. Horizontal axis (day/month/yr) -

2.5.4 Microbial biomass and activity

Soil microbial biomass C was not affected by re-wilding ($F_{1,10} = 0.02$, $P = 0.88$), but it varied across sampling dates ($F_{4,37} = 18.3$, $P < 0.0001$; Fig. 2.5a), being greatest in May and July 2007 (88.7 ± 14.0 g C m⁻² and 83.3 ± 26.7 g C m⁻² respectively, averaged across sites), and lowest in June 2008 (9.5 ± 2.7 g C m⁻²). Microbial biomass N was reduced by 30 % as a result of re-wilding ($F_{1,10} = 21.1$, $P = 0.001$, 14.1 ± 1.7 vs 19.7 ± 2.1 and g N m⁻² in re-wilding and grazed treatments respectively, Fig. 2.5c), and, when averaged across management types, it was greatest in both July 2007 and June 2008 in comparison with the rest of the sampling dates ($F_{4,39} = 26.6$, $P < 0.0001$). Re-wilding did not affect the C: N ratio of the microbial biomass ($F_{1,10} = 0.001$, $P = 0.97$), although this measure varied with sampling date ($F_{4,39} = 6.7$, $P < 0.001$) as a result of the low ratios recorded on June 2008 (Fig. 2.5b). Re-wilding caused a 20 % reduction in soil basal respiration ($F_{1,10} = 10.9$, $P < 0.0001$; 6.4 ± 0.8 μ L vs 8.1 ± 0.8 CO₂ g soil⁻¹ h⁻¹ in re-wilding and grazed treatments respectively, Fig. 2.5d). Basal respiration also varied seasonally ($F_{4,38} = 14.3$, $P < 0.0001$), being greatest in May 2007 in comparison with the rest of the dates (12.9 ± 0.7 and 7 ± 0.7 μ L CO₂ g soil⁻¹ h⁻¹ respectively). An analysis of soil properties related to N cycling showed that there was a positive correlation between N in microbial biomass and DON (Kendall's rank correlation coefficient (τ) = 0.56, $z = 6.4$, $P < 0.001$), and a less strong, but marginally significant relationship between microbial N and NH₄⁺ mineralisation rate ($\tau = 0.17$, $z = 1.8$, $P = 0.06$).

2.5.5 Soil water table and moisture content

Soil water table depth was not affected by re-wilding ($F_{1,78} = 0.82$, $P = 0.36$). However, the management by date interaction was marginally significant ($F_{8,78} = 1.95$, $P = 0.06$),

Figure 2.5: Effects of re-wilding (G^0) vs sheep grazing (G^+) across seasons on: a) soil microbial biomass C; b) microbial biomass N; c) C: N ratio in microbial biomass; and d) basal soil respiration (a measurement of microbial activity). All data are mean \pm se, per data point $n = 6$. Horizontal axis (day/month/yr) -

in that the water table was higher in the re-wilding than the grazed area in July 2007 until the September sampling date of that year, but this trend was reversed in the autumn months of October and November 2008 (Fig. 2.6a). Water table height varied greatly across sampling dates ($F_{8,78} = 11.67$, $P < 0.0001$). Despite not affecting soil water table depth, gravimetric soil moisture content was invariably greater in the re-wilding area ($F_{1,39} = 10.9$, $P < 0.005$, 562 ± 26 vs 468 ± 28 % between re-wilding and grazed area respectively) and in the May, October and January sampling dates ($F_{4,39} = 5.1$, $P < 0.005$). Finally, except for May 2007, soil bulk density was reduced as a result of re-wilding ($F_{1,39} = 2.9$, $P = 0.02$) and did not show any seasonal variation ($F_{4,39} = 1.5$, $P = 0.2$).

2.6 Discussion

Our objective was to determine how landscape level re-wilding of grass-dominated moorland affects both vegetation and soil biological properties related to C and N cycling. We found that land abandonment after 7 years strongly altered vegetation (in terms of plant functional groups, and biomass of the litter horizon) and certain soil properties. In terms of plant functional groups, re-wilding resulted in an increase in the abundance of dwarf-shrubs and a decrease in graminoids. These changes in vegetation composition have been widely observed after cessation of grazing in different upland areas of the United Kingdom (Rawes, 1981, 1983; Marrs et al., 1989; Hill et al., 1992), and are generally attributed to an increase in competitive ability of grazing sensitive dwarf-shrubs when grazing pressure is released. Aboveground biomass was larger in the re-wilding area in two of our sampling dates, but this measure was too variable to detect an overall positive effect of re-wilding across the entire sampling period. High year-to-year and

Figure 2.6: a) Effects of re-wilding (G^0) vs sheep grazing (G^+) across seasons on water table depth; b) monthly precipitation from a meteorological station near the field site. Bars = monthly precipitation for the duration of the study. Stars = 1997-2007 monthly average (data source: MIDAS Land Surface Station Data, Met Office UK). In a) all data are mean \pm se -

spatial variability in aboveground biomass has been observed in other upland ecosystems (Marrs et al., 1989; Hill et al., 1992; Milne et al., 2002), and although re-wilding has been associated to increases in standing crop biomass, response of aboveground biomass to grazing exclusion in temperate uplands is generally highly variable (Welch and Rawes, 1964).

Re-wilding also had a strong effect on the litter (L) horizon, increasing the amount of litter accumulated on the soil surface by some 70 %. Welch and Rawes (1964) reported similar increases in the size of the L horizon after exclusion of grazing at Moor House in northern England, and after a similar time interval as that elapsed in our study. Moreover, in a reassessment of the same areas in Moor House, Marrs et al. (1989) observed that after 30 years differences in the size of the L horizon between grazing-exclusions and grazed areas became larger than those observed here. The increase in the size of the L horizon might be related to high biomass allocation to litter by the dwarf-shrubs that became dominant in the re-wilding area, and also the generally lower decomposability of dwarf-shrub litter which is known to be higher in concentration of condensed tannins and phenolics (van Vuuren et al., 1992). Furthermore, it is well known that grazing increases plant biomass turnover rates through consumption (Cebrian, 1999), so its absence in the re-wilding area might translate into a build-up of litter. Although we did not measure C content in the L horizon, Ward et al. (2007) observed that grazing-exclusion led to a 35 % accumulation of C in litter in Moor House over 60 years, which highlights the potential of re-wilding to increase this C pool in moorland ecosystems in the longer term.

Re-wilding also resulted in changes in some soil properties that are typically associated with slow nutrient cycles (Bardgett and Wardle, 2003) and which have been widely observed across gradients of grazing-intensification in temperate upland habitats

(Bardgett et al., 1993, 2001). In particular, re-wilding caused significant reductions in soil basal respiration, a measure of heterotrophic microbial activity, and rates of NH_4^+ mineralisation, which are also indicative of a reduction in microbial activity in soils. As mentioned, these findings are consistent with other studies of temperate grasslands that have shown that cessation grazing reduces biological activity and rates of N cycling in soils (Bardgett et al., 1993, 1997, 2001). This response is most likely due to the lack of input of animal excreta, which is known to stimulate microbial activity and nutrient cycling in grassland soil (McNaughton et al., 1988; Augustine et al., 2003; Bardgett and Wardle, 2003), and to changes in vegetation composition that alter the quality and quantity of organic matter entering soil. For example, the increase of litter accumulation in the re-wilding area was mainly from dwarf-shrubs which, as already mentioned, are known to have lower chemical quality (e.g., higher concentration of condensed tannins and phenolics) and decomposability (Berendse, 1998; van Vuuren et al., 1992). Then, lower chemical quality may have contributed to the decrease in soil microbial activity and N mineralisation in the re-wilding area.

The increase in the ratio of DON to DIN and reduction in microbial biomass N due to re-wilding is also potentially indicative of an overall slowing down of N cycling. As shown recently by Farrell et al. (2011), the ratio of DON to DIN is typically higher in low compared to high productivity grassland ecosystems, which has been attributed to constraints on microbial activity which reduce DON turnover rates in low productivity ecosystems (Farrell et al., 2011; Schimel and Bennett, 2004). In our case, the use of N in microbial biomass as an indicator of changes in ecosystem N status is more complicated as we did not measure concomitant changes in plant N pools (e.g., Bardgett et al., 2002). Nevertheless, we did detect a positive correlation between microbial N and NH_4^+

mineralisation; and between microbial biomass N and DON. These correlations indicate that both inorganic and organic N pools might be regulated by microbial biomass as found by Zeller et al. (2001) in the case of microbial biomass N and total N in a sub-alpine grassland. Some of the changes we observed between the grazed and the re-wilding areas could also be a result of an increase in soil moisture content in the latter. However, soil humidity was extremely high on both areas and re-wilding did not affect overall the depth of the soil water table, which suggests that moisture was not a major factor explaining differences in microbial activity and N cycling between sites.

As mentioned earlier, re-wilding of overgrazed degraded moorlands has been given a high conservation priority in the United Kingdom (Pakeman et al., 2003; Milligan et al., 2004; Littlewood et al., 2006; Mitchell et al., 2008) in order to restore the main vegetation attributes and associated fauna of these ecosystems (Reed et al., 2009). We enquired whether re-wilding could also influence other ecosystem services, particularly the potential to sequester C and N in soils, which is a key aspect in ecosystem services valuation (Dominati et al., 2010; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), and is of high relevance to current land management policies (Sutherland et al., 2006). Despite re-wilding resulting in a slowing down cycling of N cycling and a build up of litter on the soil surface, we did not observe a concomitant change in total soil C or N. This might imply that, so far, not enough time has been elapsed for changes on these soil properties to be affected by re-wilding, which is consistent with other studies of moorland ecosystems that likewise show a lack of response of soil C to removal of grazing, even after more than 30 years (Marrs et al., 1989; Garnett et al., 2000; Ward et al., 2007). These results collectively suggest that re-wilding of moorlands via the removal of domestic herbivores is unlikely to reap benefits for soil C sequestration, at least in the short term

(i.e., decades). More research is needed to corroborate this conclusion as high variation in grazing effects on soil C has been reported (Conant et al., 2001; Reeder and Schuman, 2002; Cui et al., 2005; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010).

Together with total soil C and N, re-wilding did not modify other key soil properties including DOC, DON and microbial C. Dissolved organic matter (including DOC and DON) is a key component in the C and N fluxes in systems with highly organic soils such as those of our study (Freeman et al., 2001). We did not record any effect of re-wilding on these properties, but they showed strong seasonal differences with higher values associated to periods characterised by warm temperatures. Likewise, Ward et al. (2007) observed that season was more important than grazing in explaining the variation in DOC concentrations in moorlands, and they attributed DOC concentration control to a combination of environmental factors (warm temperatures and reduction in soil water saturation) which lead to higher microbial activity. On the other hand, although it has been shown that bottom-up controls on soil microbial biomass are rather idiosyncratic (Bardgett and Wardle, 2010), the lack of response of microbial biomass C to re-wilding could be explained by the fact that re-wilding did not affect root biomass.

2.6.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, after almost a decade of re-wilding, we detected significant changes in vegetation and some signs of a slowing down of C and N cycling in moorlands. However, despite this, and a significant build up in surface litter as a result of re-wilding, this has not yet translated into any change in stocks of C and N in soil, which is a key goal of moorland restoration management.

Chapter 3

Plant and soil responses to defoliation: A comparative study of grass species with contrasting life history strategies

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2. Plant and soil responses to defoliation: A comparative study of grass species with contrasting life history strategies

3.1 Abstract

The overall aim of this study was to test for inter-species variation in plant and soil responses to defoliation among a broad range of temperate grass species and life-history strategies. We used a microcosm experiment where a range of grass species differing in life history traits were subjected to different intensities of defoliation, and a range of aboveground and belowground plant and soil responses were measured. All plant attributes, including accumulated shoot biomass, root biomass and root length, showed a strong negative response to defoliation, although plant species exhibited subtle differences in the way that they responded to increased severity of defoliation. Defoliation also exerted a strong influence on soil properties, decreasing soil microbial carbon (C) and the soil microbial C:nitrogen (N) ratio, and increasing inorganic N availability and potential N mineralisation across all species. Despite the wide range in life history strategies, plant species did not differ in their influence on most of the soil variables, except for the rate of nitrate mineralisation, which was lowest under plant species that displayed the least relative detrimental responses to defoliation. Collectively, our results suggest that plant and soil responses to defoliation are reasonably consistent across a broad range of grass species, with only subtle inter-specific differences among species.

3.2 Keywords

Defoliation, microbial biomass, grassland, nitrogen cycling, herbivory, life history strategies.

3.3 Introduction

The last few decades have witnessed an increasing attention being devoted to understanding the role that grazers play in regulating soil biogeochemical processes (Bardgett and Wardle, 2010). This research has shown how grazing can modify a number of ecosystem properties, all of which ultimately impact on rates of soil nutrient cycling with feedback consequences for primary production. For example, grazing-induced increases in soil compaction (Cumming and Cumming, 2003), alterations of soil water regimes (Medina-Roldán et al., 2007), plant species composition (Ritchie et al., 1998; Wardle et al., 2001), and aboveground and belowground primary productivity (Milchunas and Lauenroth, 1993; Burke et al., 1998) are regularly cited as drivers of soil nutrient dynamics. Also, grazing animals can affect the spatial distribution of nutrients within ecosystems as a result of their movements and patchy return of nutrients in excreta, which in turn influences vegetation patterns (de Mazancourt et al., 1998; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010). Over time scales from days to months, plant responses to biomass removal, or defoliation, act as a key mechanism by which grazing affects soil nutrient dynamics. Defoliation has been shown to alter plant allocation patterns, in terms of both root biomass (Mikola et al., 2001a) and root exudation (Paterson and Sim, 1999, 2000). These changes in plant allocation can, in turn, have cascading effects on below-

ground food-webs, modifying microbial abundance and activity (Guitian and Bardgett, 2000; Mikola et al., 2001a; Hamilton III and Frank, 2001) and the abundance of microbial predators (Mikola et al., 2001a, 2009; Hokka et al., 2004). All together, the effects on belowground food-webs mediated by defoliation have been linked to increases in soil nutrient mineralisation and availability (Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Mikola et al., 2001a), and this is thought to contribute to the compensatory response of plant growth to herbivory (Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Mikola et al., 2009).

Past studies suggest that plant and soil responses to defoliation vary across plant species and with the frequency of defoliation (Chapin III and Slack, 1979; Briske, 1996; Guitian and Bardgett, 2000; Klironomos et al., 2004; Ilmarinen et al., 2005; Gastal et al., 2010). Such differential responses of plant species to defoliation have been explained on the basis of plant functional traits which influence soil-resource dynamics, such as root exudates entering into the decomposers food-web (Holland et al., 1996; Mawdsley and Bardgett, 1997; Mikola and Kytöviita, 2002), and traits directly linked to the uptake of nutrients and competition for these with soil microbes such as root biomass and root length density (Chapin III and Slack, 1979; Oosterheld, 1992). Most studies on this topic, however, have focused on a handful of plant species, and none, as far as we are aware, have comprehensively and simultaneously tested the responses of a broad range of plant species to defoliation. As a result, little is known about the differential response of grassland plant species and their associated soil microbial communities to defoliation, and this hampers our ability to draw generalizations about plant and soil responses to grazing in grassland ecosystems. Here, we redress this lack of knowledge by testing for inter-species variation in plant and soil responses to defoliation among a broad range of temperate grass species and life-history strategies. Specifically, we test

the hypotheses that soil biological properties related to N cycling would be correlated with the particular response of a plant species to defoliation (i.e., soil responses could be predicted from the defoliation response of the plants). This was done by measuring aboveground and belowground plant responses of a range of common UK grass species to different intensities of defoliation, and associated changes in soil microbial biomass and rates of N cycling, in a glasshouse microcosm experiment.

3.4 Material and methods

3.4.1 Experimental set-up

A range of seven common British grass species occurring on different habitat types and representing a spectrum of life histories including response to grazing and defoliation (see Table 3.1 for a summary of RGR_{max} , RGR_{mean} , C-S-R strategy, Ellenberg numbers, and grazing and defoliation response), were grown in a glasshouse experiment during the spring of 2007 at Lancaster University, U.K. Briefly, seeds (Ermorsgate Seeds, Norfolk, UK) of the grass species *Nardus stricta* L., *Anthoxanthum odoratum* L., *Festuca rubra* L., *Poa pratensis* L., *Agrostis capillaris* L., *Lolium perenne* L., and *Holcus lanatus* L. (nomenclature follows Clapham et al., 1987), were germinated on a 1 : 1(w/w) mixture of commercial acidic sand and Levingtons M3 growing media. The slow growing species *N. stricta* was sown 6 weeks before the rest of the grasses in order to reduce differences in plant size which are inherently dependent on the wide range in RGR_{max} employed in this study (Grime and Hunt, 1975) (Table 3.1). Established seedlings were transplanted into pots (11 x 11 cm, height and diameter) following a similar design as that used by Guitian and Bardgett (2000). Pots' substratum was composed of a nutrient-poor

3.4 Material and methods

soil (N % = 0.6) coming from and acidic (pH in H₂O = 4.5) soil taken from a semi-natural *Festuca ovina*-*Agrostis capillaris* grassland (National Vegetation Classification: U4b, Rodwell, 1992) located in Littledale, Lancashire, UK (Bardgett et al., 2003). Two weeks later, each grass species planted in the experimental pots was randomly assigned to 1 out of 3 defoliation treatments simulating different intensities of grazing, namely: 1) control plants without defoliation (CN); 2) light defoliated plants, clipped each 2 weeks (MC); and 3) heavy defoliated plants clipped at weekly intervals (HC). The defoliation treatment was imposed over an 8-week period and consisted of the removal of above-ground tissue at 4 cm above the soil surface. Treatments were applied in a randomised block design with 4 replicates per plant species and defoliation treatment combination, yielding a total of 84 pots (7 species x 3 defoliation x 4 blocks). Plants were watered on every other day and remained in a glasshouse in Lancaster University with the following settings: 12 hours light-night periods providing a mean irradiance of 430 Wm⁻², mean day temperature of 22 °C, and a mean night temperature of 18 °C.

3.4.2 Measurement of aboveground variables

Before applying the defoliation treatments, initial shoot biomass was calculated in order to use this measure as a covariate for statistical analyses, and hence rule out size-specific effects of different plant species on response variables. This calculation was based on species-specific allometric relationships between leaf length and shoot biomass of a subset of grass seedlings (*N. stricta*, $y = -6.79x^{1.1871}$, $R^2 = 0.87$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 17$; *A. odoratum*, $y = -6.3x^{1.2768}$, $R^2 = 0.97$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 6$; *F. ovina*, $y = -4.64x^{0.9617}$, $R^2 = 0.96$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 18$; *H. lanatus*, $y = -5.37x^{1.1667}$, $R^2 = 0.78$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 20$; *P. pratensis*, $y = -3.53x^{0.9433}$, $R^2 = 0.95$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 17$; *A. capillaris*, $y =$

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Table 3.1: Some ecological traits of the species selected for the experimental study. R_{max} = maximum relative growth rate (week^{-1}), R_{mean} = mean relative growth rate (week^{-1}). See references for details.

Species	R_{max}	R_{mean}	Ref.	CSR strategy	Ref.	Ellenberg number	Ref.	Grazing response	Ref.
<i>N. stricta</i>	0.71	0.71	1	S-SC	2	-	-	Increaser under sheep grazing	6
<i>A. odoratum</i>	0.94	0.94	1	SR-CSR	2	3	3	Increaser under rabbit grazing	5
<i>F. rubra</i>	1.18	1.18	1	C-S-R (but variable) populations in C, S-C or S	2	3	3	Decreaser under rabbit grazing	5
<i>P. pratensis</i>	1.26	1.26	1	C-S-R	2	6	4	Grazing tolerant	7
<i>L. perenne</i>	1.3	1.3	1	CR-CSR	2	7	3	-	-
<i>A. capillaris</i>	1.36	1.36	1	C-S-R	2	4	4	Increaser under rabbit grazing	6
<i>H. lanatus</i>	2.01	1.56	1	C-S-R	2	5	4	Decreaser under rabbit grazing	6

References (Ref):

1. Grime and Hunt (1975)
2. Grime et al. (2007)
3. Elberse and Berendse (1993)
4. Hill and Carey (1997)
5. Crawley (1990)
6. Welch (1986)
7. Hamilton III and Frank (2001)

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$-7.45x^{1.24}$, $R^2 = 0.96$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 18$; and $L. perenne$, $y = -6.73x^{1.238}$, $R^2 = 0.93$, $P < 0.001$, $n = 17$). We, then, estimated leaf length in the experimental pots (digital images analysed in JMicroVision for linux; (Roduit, 2007)) and initial shoot biomass was calculated based on the estimated leaf lengths using the aforementioned allometric parameters. At the end of the experiment, all aboveground plant biomass was harvested from each pot and combined with that collected from previous clippings to determine total shoot biomass (after 70 °C drying for 48 h) produced over the experimental period.

3.4.3 Measurement of belowground variables

Plant root systems were manually removed from each pot to estimate root-related variables. Total root length was estimated by species-specific allometric relationships between root length and root mass from root sub-samples. First, we scanned sub-samples of the fresh root systems in a conventional scanner (CanoScan 4200F, Canon Inc. Tokyo Japan). Roots were submerged into water in an acrylic tray avoiding root overlapping as much as possible and scanned in a 300 dpi resolution. These digital images were analysed using an image analysis software (ImageJ, (Rasband, 2007)) by the method described in Kimura et al. (1999), and this estimation of root length was used to model total root length using total root mass as the predictor. This approach produced highly significant parameters to estimate total root length for all species (data not included). Root dry biomass (including grass crowns) was determined by oven-drying the roots as with aboveground biomass. Soil collected after root recovery was passed through a 2 mm mesh sieve and stored at 4 °C before the analytical assays were carried out. Microbial biomass carbon (C) and N were determined by extracting 5 g of soil (fresh basis)

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in 25 mL of 0.5 M K_2SO_4 of both 24h- $CHCl_3$ fumigated and unfumigated soil samples (Vance et al., 1987). Soil- K_2SO_4 extracts were shaken for 30 min and filtered through a 1-grade Whatman paper. Microbial biomass C was calculated as the difference in total C in fumigated and unfumigated soil extracts, determined with a Shimadzu 5000A TOC analyser (Shimadzu Inc., Japan) and using an extraction efficiency factor (ke_C) of 0.45 (Sparling et al., 1990). Microbial biomass N was measured as the difference in total N ($N-NH_4^+$ and $N-NO_3^-$) produced by the persulfate digestion method (Cabrera and Beare, 1993) between fumigated and unfumigated soil extracts, measured by automated continuous flow colorimetry in a Bran and Luebbe AutoAnalyser 3. The extraction efficiency factor (ke_N) used for N in microbial biomass was 0.54 (Brookes et al., 1985).

Potential NH_4^+ mineralisation rate was determined by measuring the $N-NH_4^+$ difference between KCl extracts of incubated and non-incubated soil samples (Campbell et al., 1993; Harrison and Bardgett, 2010). Non-incubated samples were extracted without previous incubation, whereas incubated samples were held for a period of 14 days in sealed sterile bottles at 25 °C. Extractions were made with 10 g of fresh soil extracted in 50 ml 1 M KCl, shaken for 60 min and filtered through a 1-grade Whatman paper. Ammonium mineralisation rate was calculated as $(N-NH_4^+ t_{14} - N-NH_4^+ t_0)/(14 \text{ days})$ ($mg N-NH_4^+ kg \text{ dry soil}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$). Nitrate mineralisation rate was determined following the same procedure as for $N-NH_4^+$, but for $N-NO_3^-$. Both $N-NH_4^+$ and $N-NO_3^-$ in KCl extracts were measured by automated continuous flow colorimetry as described above.

3.4.4 Statistical analyses

All variables were tested for normality with the Shapiro-Wilks test and normalised if necessary (Zar, 1998). Data were analysed using ANOVA with plant species and defoliation as fixed experimental factors, and blocks as a random factor by using general linear mixed models (Pinheiro et al., 2008). For plant-related variables (aboveground and belowground biomass, root length, and specific root length), ANCOVA was used to test the effect of plant species and defoliation including initial shoot biomass as a covariate term and models' estimates were corrected depending on the significance of these term (Engqvist, 2005). Estimated shoot initial biomass (see aboveground variables) values were (average dry weight (mg) \pm standard deviation): *N. stricta* (22.68 \pm 15.09), *F. rubra* (60.7 \pm 12.76), *P. pratensis* (160.88 \pm 43.52), *H. lanatus* (310.41 \pm 39.4), *A. odoratum* (373.87 \pm 134.17), *A. capillaris* (16.86 \pm 3.08), and *L. perenne* (165.23 \pm 49.48); thus justifying its use in the ANCOVA models. All statistical tests were carried out with the R statistical package for Linux (R Development Core Team, 2010).

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Aboveground responses

At final harvest, the extent that total accumulated shoot biomass was reduced by defoliation varied among the grass species, as shown by the significant defoliation by species interaction ($F_{12,57} = 7$, $P < 0.0001$, Fig. 3.1a). Reductions in total accumulated shoot biomass resulting from defoliation were more pronounced for *F. rubra*, *H. lanatus*, *A. odoratum* and *A. capillaris* when defoliation intensity was low (72, 56, 65

and 57 % reductions in shoot biomass between lightly-clipped and undefoliated controls, respectively) than under more severe defoliation (6, 20, 7 and 38 % reductions in shoot biomass between heavy and light defoliation, respectively). In contrast, decreases in shoot biomass of *P. pratensis* and *N. stricta* were of a similar magnitude across the defoliation frequency treatments. Finally, shoot biomass of *L. perenne* increased under light defoliation but decreased moderately under heavy-defoliation frequency. Individual ANOVA's for each single species (note that cross-species comparisons are not valid for these analyses) showed that species roughly grouped into those whose shoot biomass significantly decreased for both defoliation frequencies (*A. capillaris*, *H. lanatus* and *P. pratensis*); those which were sensitive to light but not high defoliation (i.e., no difference between lightly- and heavily-defoliated plants: *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra* and *N. stricta*); and *L. perenne* which, although responsive to defoliation, did not show a clear separation among defoliation intensities because it yielded a very low shoot biomass in the undefoliated controls (Fig. 3.1a).

3.5.2 Belowground responses

Root biomass decreased strongly in response to defoliation across all plant species ($F_{2,55} = 140.5$, $P < 0.0001$, Fig. 3.1b). Unlike shoot biomass, the decrease in root biomass in response to defoliation was similar for all species (species x defoliation interaction effect, $F_{12,55} = 1.5$, $P = 0.17$), and all species showed a high sensitivity to light defoliation (an average 71 % reduction between light defoliation and controls). *Post-hoc* test showed that there were no differences between the means for the light- and heavy-frequency defoliation in *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra*, and *N. stricta* (data not shown). Plant species significantly differed in root biomass ($F_{6,55} = 18$, $P < 0.0001$, values for

Figure 3.1: Plant response to different intensities of defoliation across a broad range of common grass species, including: a) total accumulated shoot biomass; b) belowground biomass; c) root: shoot ratio; and d) total root length (as estimated from allometric equations fitted to root mass and root length data estimated by image analysis). Labels are: UN = non-defoliated controls; LC = light defoliation (defoliation each two weeks); and HD= heavy defoliation (weekly). N.st = *Nardus stricta*, A.od = *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, F.ru = *Festuca rubra*, P.pr = *Poa pratensis*, L.pe = *Lolium perenne*, A.ca = *Agrostis capillaris*, H.la = *Holcus lanatus*. All values are back-transformed means \pm se. In the case of aboveground biomass, values are adjusted means \pm adjusted se as determined by ANCOVA with biomass in the beginning of experiment being the significant covariate -

the individual q statistics of the Tukey's test not included) in the order *H. lanatus* > *A. odoratum* > *A. capillaris* = *N. stricta* = *L. perenne* > *P. pratensis* > *F. rubra*.

We detected a significant defoliation by species interaction for the root to shoot mass ratio (R:S) ($F_{12,55} = 3$, $P = 0.004$) which provides additional evidence that plant species responded differently across the two defoliation frequencies (Fig. 3.1c). No clear relationship could be observed for the reductions in R:S in response to defoliation or in relation to species life history strategy, at least based on published values of RGR_{max} .

Total root length (TRL) decreased in response to defoliation (Fig. 3.1d), and this reduction varied among the plant species with defoliation frequency as shown by the species by defoliation interaction ($F_{12,52} = 2$, $P < 0.05$). *A. capillaris* and *P. pratensis* showed similar reductions in TRL across the two defoliation frequencies (*A. capillaris* = 71 % reduction between the undefoliated control and light defoliation, and 55 % between light defoliation and the heavy defoliation treatment; *P. pratensis* = 65 and 57 % for the same treatments respectively). On the other hand, the reduction in TRL of *L. perenne* was higher when defoliation frequency increased (33 % reduction between undefoliated controls and light defoliation and 55 % reduction between light and heavy defoliation respectively). *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra*, *H. lanatus* and *N. stricta* were relatively insensitive to heavy defoliation, displaying only a low reduction in TRL from the low to the high intensity treatment. Individual ANOVA's for each single species (data not shown) showed basically the same patterns as those already described, i.e., a group of species which responded consistently negative to increasing frequency of defoliation (*A. capillaris*, *H.lanatus*, *L. perenne* and *P. pratensis*) and other which was sensitive to low but insensitive to high frequency defoliation (as shown by the means differences between these treatments, *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra* and *N. stricta*). Since we used root

mass in our species-specific estimations of TRL, statistical analysis of specific root length would produce more or less the same qualitative results as those for root mass. However, results among species can portray some insight on the extent of the costs species incurred in terms of root production (with lower values indicating higher construction costs). Specific root length followed the sequence *L. perenne* (110 ± 10) < *F. rubra* (137 ± 11) < *P. pratensis* (141 ± 14) < *N. stricta* (143 ± 22) < *H. lanatus* (169 ± 14) < *A. odoratum* (172 ± 11) < *A. capillaris* ($172 \pm 12 \text{ mg}^{-1}$) respectively).

We used principal component analysis (PCA) on transformed response variables (aboveground and belowground biomass, root to shoot ratio and total root length) to summarize plant species responses to defoliation. The first PCA axis explained 78 % of the variance in the data and was associated with defoliation frequency, with belowground plant attributes (i.e., root mass and total root length) having the highest loads on this first component (see Fig. A.1).

3.5.3 Soil responses

When data were integrated across all species, light and heavy frequency defoliation reduced microbial biomass C in soil ($F_{2,53} = 7.5$, $P < 0.01$, Fig. 3.2a). Microbial biomass C was reduced from 2040 ± 147 (mean \pm se) mg C kg^{-1} in soil of control plants to 1480 ± 71 and $1465 \pm 102 \text{ mg C kg}^{-1}$ in soil of plants under moderate and heavy defoliation frequency respectively, and this reduction in microbial C was correlated to reductions in root biomass caused by defoliation ($r = 0.36$, $t_{74} = 3.5$, $P = 0.001$). *Post-hoc* analyses showed, however, that microbial C means across defoliation frequencies were significantly different only for *H. lanatus* and *A. capillaris*; and for *A. odoratum* between the undefoliated and the clipped-treatments (Fig. 3.2a). In contrast, defoliation did not

Figure 3.2: Responses to different intensities of defoliation across a broad range of common grass species of soil microbial biomass carbon (a); soil microbial nitrogen (b); and the microbial C: N ratio (c). UN = undefoliated controls; LD = light-defoliation (defoliation each two weeks); HD= heavy defoliation (weekly). N.st = *Nardus stricta*, A.od = *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, F.ru = *Festuca rubra*, P.pr = *Poa pratensis*, L.pe = *Lolium perenne*, A.ca = *Agrostis capillaris*, H.la = *Holcus lanatus*. All values are means \pm se. -

affect microbial biomass N ($F_{2,54} = 1.5$, $P = 0.26$, Fig. 3.2b); hence, across all plant species, microbial C:N ratio was reduced by 20.0 and 25.6 % under moderate and heavy defoliation, respectively, when compared with the undefoliated control ($F_{2,53} = 8.5$, $P < 0.001$, Fig. 3.2c).

Soil N availability was also affected by defoliation treatments (Fig. 3.3a). Across all plant species, heavy defoliation increased soil NH_4^+ ($F_{2,54} = 3$, $P = 0.05$) and total inorganic N ($F_{2,54} = 3$, $P = 0.05$) concentrations by 35 % and 29 % respectively compared to the undefoliated control. Mean comparison tests showed significant differences in *N. stricta* and *A. capillaris* between undefoliated controls and the defoliated treatments but not in the rest of the species. Soil NO_3^- concentrations were not significantly affected by defoliation ($F_{2,54} = 3$, $P > 0.05$, Fig. 3.3b), although potential net nitrification rate increased by almost 200 % under heavy defoliation ($F_{2,54} = 3.5$, $P < 0.05$) relative to the undefoliated controls (Fig. 3.3c). The rate of net nitrate mineralisation also varied significantly among plant species ($F_{6,54} = 3.5$, $P < 0.01$, Fig. 3.3c), being greatest in soil planted with *N. stricta* (2.9 ± 1.9 mg NO_3^- kg soil $^{-1}$ day $^{-1}$) and lowest in soil of *A. capillaris* (0.21 ± 0.22 mg NO_3^- kg soil $^{-1}$ day $^{-1}$). The sequence of NO_3^- mineralisation after *post-hoc* tests was, in descending order, *N. stricta*, *L. perenne*, *F. rubra*, *P. pratensis*, *H. lanatus*, *A. odoratum*, and *A. capillaris*. Some plant species at the fast-growing end of the life history gradient had the lowest values of net NO_3^- mineralisation, but the overall trend was erratic (non significant species x defoliation interaction). *Post-hoc* tests showed that means differences between heavy defoliation and the other treatments were significant for *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra*, *H. lanatus* and *P. pratensis*. Neither net potential NH_4^+ nor total N mineralisation rates (Fig. 3.3d) were affected by the experimental treatments and grass species identity did not, in general,

influence soil variables, aside potential net NO_3^- mineralisation rate as already stated.

3.6 Discussion

In this study, we tested whether plant responses to defoliation vary across a range of grassland plant species representing a broad range in life-history strategies, and whether soil microbial and biogeochemical responses to defoliation were related to such inter-species variation. We detected a general detrimental effect of defoliation on shoot and root growth among all plant species tested, and subtle inter-specific differences in the response to defoliation frequency. In particular, *A. capillaris* and *H. lanatus* showed consistently higher absolute values in shoot and root biomass and root length and relatively lower losses in root attributes across defoliation treatments, but their performance was reduced when defoliation was intensified (from light to heavy defoliation frequencies). The same reductions in response to defoliation were observed in *P. pratensis* and *L. perenne*, but these later species displayed low absolute values in plant measures. Yet another group of species, *A. odoratum*, *F. rubra* and *N. stricta*, showed no additional decreases in performance between light and severe defoliation in most of our plant measures which we interpret here as a sign of resistance to defoliation. Abundance of *N. stricta* is often high in grazed grasslands (Welch, 1986), which is attributed to its unpalatable shoot tissue (Massey et al., 2007), and Hartley and Amos (1999) report that defoliation (a less severe regime than that used here) did not cause reductions in root length of *N. stricta* plants, adding evidence that this species is resistant to defoliation. There is evidence of *F. rubra* showing compensatory growth responses to grazing as well (Berg et al., 1997; van der Graaf et al., 2005). Several other studies have likewise found declines in root productivity in response to defoliation (Guitian and Bardgett, 2000; Mikola et al.,

Figure 3.3: Soil responses to different intensities of defoliation across a broad range of common grass species, including ammonium availability (a), mineral soil N (ammonium+nitrate) (b), net potential nitrate mineralisation rate (c) and the total N mineralisation rate (ammonium+nitrate) (d); U= undefoliated controls; LD = light defoliation (defoliation each two weeks); HC= heavy defoliation (weekly). N.st = *Nardus stricta*, A.od = *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, F.ru = *Festuca rubra*, P.pr = *Poa pratensis*, L.pe = *Lolium perenne*, A.ca = *Agrostis capillaris*, H.la = *Holcus lanatus*. All values are means \pm se. -

2001a), although evidence is mixed. For example, fenced exclusion studies on Serengeti grasslands show that mammalian grazers do not necessarily inhibit root biomass and productivity (McNaughton et al., 1998), and in a global literature synthesis Milchunas and Lauenroth (1993) reported both enhancements and reductions in root biomass as a result of herbivore exclusion. More recently in a meta-analysis on graminoids, Ferraro and Oesterheld (2002) showed that the effects of defoliation are less acute on root than on shoot biomass. Nevertheless, our analysis showed that root mass and root length are important attributes in describing inter-specific differences in response to defoliation. Root length is a measure of plant foraging scale (Kembel et al., 2005) and therefore it might be associated with the response of grasses to defoliation.

In general, the detrimental response of plant growth to defoliation was mirrored in the soil biological properties measured, although inter-specific differences were not detected. Across all plant species, defoliation was found to reduce microbial biomass and its C: N ratio, and to increase NH_4^+ availability and the rate of NO_3^- mineralisation. The negative response of microbial biomass C to defoliation that we observed contrasts sharply with results of a number of experimental studies, which have found that defoliation stimulates soil microbes (Mawdsley and Bardgett, 1997; Bardgett et al., 1998; Mikola et al., 2001b). Increases in microbial biomass following defoliation have been attributed to the stimulation of root exudation (Holland, 1995; Holland et al., 1996; Mawdsley and Bardgett, 1997; Hamilton III et al., 2008), and this stimulation of root exudates as a result of clipping has been reported for some of the plant species used in our experiment, namely *L. perenne* and *F. rubra* (Paterson and Sim, 1999, 2000). Our findings indicate, however, that defoliation caused soil microbes to become limited by C, as evidenced by the decline in the microbial C:N ratio, which is indicative of increase

in C relative to N limitation (Kaye and Hart, 1997). This decline is also likely to be related to the reduction in root biomass across all species as a result of defoliation, a view supported by the positive correlation of root biomass with microbial biomass C. The lack of effect that increasing the intensity of defoliation had on microbial biomass C is likely explained by the relatively large effect that light defoliation had on plant performance relative to the undefoliated controls. The decline in microbial biomass C could also be partly due to increased predation by soil animals, given that previous studies have shown that defoliation enhances the abundances of microbial-feeding faunal groups in soil (Mikola et al., 2001a,b). However, in our study, it is most likely that reductions in root C allocation under defoliation, and hence C supply to soil, is the main cause of the consistent decline in microbial biomass across all defoliated plant species (Mikola et al., 2001a; Bazot et al., 2005; Hamilton III et al., 2008; Sankaran and Augustine, 2004).

Defoliation increased NH_4^+ and total inorganic N availability, as well as the potential rates of NO_3^- mineralisation across all species tested. A number of studies have documented a stimulatory effect of defoliation (Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Mikola et al., 2001a; Ayres et al., 2007) and ungulate grazing (Seagle et al., 1992; Hamilton III et al., 2008) on soil N availability and mineralisation, and this response is thought to be a key mechanism contributing to compensatory growth in grazed grassland (Owen, 1980; Ritchie et al., 1998; Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Bardgett et al., 2003). Such enhanced soil N mineralisation has been attributed to a variety of mechanisms, including the return of N-rich plant litter and animal wastes to soil (Day and Detling, 1990; de Mazancourt et al., 1998), and the stimulation of microbial activity and N mineralisation in the root zone due to enhanced root exudation in defoliated plants (Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Mikola et al., 2001a; Ayres et al., 2007). In our experiment, however,

we propose that the defoliation-induced increase in soil N availability and mineralisation was due to the previously mentioned switch to C limitation of the microbial biomass, as indicated by the reduction in microbial C:N across all defoliated plants. Indeed, it is well established that under conditions when microbial growth is C limited, microbes use the C to support their energy needs and they excrete plant available ammonium (NH_4^+) as a waste product into soil i.e., N is mineralised by the microbial biomass (Kaye and Hart, 1997). Microbial C limitation together with the strong negative impact of defoliation on plant size and the concomitant reduction in total plant N might be the cause for the increase in N availability. As previously mentioned, it is also possible that higher rates of microbial predation in soils of defoliated plants contributed to the stimulation of soil N availability via the microbial-loop (Clarholm, 1985), although this was not measured in this study.

Despite the wide spectrum in ecological traits in the plant species we used, and the subtle differences in plant growth responses to defoliation, few inter-specific differences were observed in the response of soil properties. Only for the rate of NO_3^- mineralisation did we detect inter-specific differences in the responses to defoliation. Here, we found that the rate of NO_3^- mineralisation was significantly lower in soils planted with the grasses which showed the highest biomass values, namely *A. capillaris*, *A. odoratum* and *H. lanatus*, than in soils planted with *N. stricta*. However, we did not detect a defoliation by species interaction, indicating that such inter-specific differences in NO_3^- mineralisation were independent of defoliation. This trend of lower rates of NO_3^- mineralisation in soils planted with those species which exhibited higher biomass values across defoliation treatments is difficult to interpret given that no concomitant changes in NH_4^+ availability were detected for the same set of species. The absence of inter-species differences in other

soil properties across the species tested is in contrast to previous studies which show that plant species, and even genotypes, can have markedly different effects on soil biological properties, acting as major determinant of microbial communities in soil (Bardgett et al., 1999b; Innes et al., 2004; Bezemer et al., 2006; Markham et al., 2008; Harrison and Bardgett, 2010; Orwin et al., 2010). We do not know the reason for the absence of such inter-species variation in soil properties in our experiment. However, given that inter-specific differences in most soil biological properties were apparent in the undefoliated controls, but not in defoliated plants, it appears that defoliation has cancelled out any differences at the species level. Secondly, it has been shown that the effects of plant species on soil properties are dependent on soil type (Innes et al., 2004; Marschner et al., 2004; Bezemer et al., 2006). In this way, it seems that our soil might have restricted the expression of strong plant effects on soil biological properties, suggesting that other factors, such as low pH and nutrient availability, might have been primary determinants of these measures. Despite this, defoliation was found to consistently and strongly promote soil nutrient availability in soil across all species tested.

In conclusion, our results show that grassland plant species representing a broad range of life history strategies respond in a consistent way to defoliation. Across all species tested, we found that defoliation reduced plant growth, especially of root mass and length, but stimulated N availability in soil. We did not measure the consequences of this defoliation-induced stimulation of N availability, but we propose that it would, in the long term, positively feedback to the plant in terms of improved N acquisition and, potentially, improved growth. Surprisingly, we found only subtle differences in the response of different plant species to defoliation, and no inter-species variation in the response of soil properties to this treatment. This suggests that, in these soils, effects

3.6 Discussion

of defoliation on plant and soil properties are remarkably consistent, at least under the experimental conditions used in this study. Overall, our findings reinforce the view that aboveground and belowground components of ecosystems are strongly interrelated and that understanding the effects of grazing on ecosystems nutrient cycling requires a combined aboveground and belowground approach.

Chapter 4

Grazing-induced effects on soil properties modify plant competitive interactions in semi-natural mountain grasslands

This chapter has been submitted to *Oecologia*, authored and under the name of: “Medina-Roldán, E., J. Paz-Ferreiro, and R.D. Bardgett. Grazing-induced effects on soil properties modify plant competitive interactions in semi-natural mountain grasslands”. Co-author JPF contributed with logistical and field work, and RDB is the supervisor of the thesis work. Manuscript is currently under review. Superficial changes were done for sake of the thesis format.

4. Grazing-induced effects on soil properties modify plant competitive interactions in semi-natural mountain grasslands

4.1 Abstract

Plant-soil feedbacks are widely recognized as playing a significant role in structuring plant communities through their effects on plant-plant interactions. However, the question of whether plant-soil feedbacks can be indirectly driven by other ecological agents, such as large herbivores which are known to strongly modify plant community structure and soil properties, remains poorly explored. Here we tested in a glasshouse experiment how changes in soil properties resulting from long-term sheep grazing affect competitive interactions (intra- and inter-specific) of two graminoid species: *Nardus stricta*, which is typically abundant under high sheep grazing pressure in British mountain grasslands, and *Eriophorum vaginatum*, whose abundance is typically diminished under grazing. Both species were grown in monocultures and mixtures at different densities in soils taken from adjacent grazed and ungrazed mountain grassland in the Yorkshire Dales, northern England. *Nardus stricta* performed better (shoot and root biomass) when grown in grazing-conditioned soil, independent of whether it grew under inter-specific competition or not. *Eriophorum vaginatum* also grew better when planted in soil from the grazed site, but this occurred only when it did not experience competition with *N. stricta*. This indicates that plant-soil feedback for *E. vaginatum* is dependent on the

presence of an inter-specific competitor. A yield density model showed that indirect effects of grazing increased the intensity of intra-specific competition in both species in comparison with ungrazed-conditioned soil. However, indirect effects of grazing on the intensity of inter-specific competition were species-specific favouring *N. stricta*. We explain these asymmetric grazing-induced effects on competition based on traits of the superior competitor and grazing effects on soil nutrients, and discuss the relevance of our findings for plant community dynamics in grazed, semi-natural grasslands.

4.2 Keywords

Grazing, community dynamics, upland grasslands, *Nardus stricta*, *Eriophorum vaginatum*, plant-soil interactions.

4.3 Introduction

The study of factors that modify plant competitive interactions is key to understanding plant community dynamics and species coexistence. A number of mechanisms and ecological factors that can modify plant competition have been identified (Aarssen, 1983, 1989; Bengtsson et al., 1994; Pacala and Tilman, 1994; Chesson, 2000; Barot, 2004). These include those that promote heterogeneity across spatial and temporal scales (Pacala and Tilman, 1994; Chesson, 2000; Barot, 2004), and others where species-specific plant responses to environmental heterogeneity (morphological, physiological or phenological) can reduce niche overlap (Casper and Jackson, 1997; Grime, 2001; McKane et al., 2002). In another line of enquiry, Bever et al. (1997) highlighted the importance of

plant-soil interactions in regulating plant competition through plant-soil feedbacks (effect that a soil where certain plant species grew has on that plant species), and since that time numerous studies have showed the importance of these aboveground- belowground linkages in structuring plant communities (van der Putten et al., 2001; Blomqvist et al., 2000; Klironomos, 2002; Bezemer et al., 2006; Casper and Castelli, 2007; Harrison and Bardgett, 2010).

It is also well known that grazing by large herbivores directly modifies plant competition by reducing dominance of some plant species through consumption (Anderson and Briske, 1995; Hartley and Amos, 1999) or through changes in disturbance regimes (Coffin and Lauenroth, 1988; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010). However, despite widespread recognition that grazing can also strongly modify soil microbial communities and rates of nutrient mineralization (Bardgett et al., 1999a; Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Frank et al., 2003), little is understood about the indirect effects of grazing on plant competitive interactions via its effects on soil properties. In temperate grasslands in particular, previous studies have shown that grazing can cause shifts in the composition of soil microbial communities leading to increases in rates of nitrogen (N) mineralization, and hence N availability to plants (Bardgett et al., 1997; Frank et al., 2000; Bardgett et al., 2001). Such changes in soil communities and nutrient availability are likely to affect plant-plant interactions through plant-soil feedbacks, thereby modifying vegetation dynamics. However, as far as we know, the potential for grazing to indirectly affect plant-plant interactions via this route has not been explored.

The aim of this study was to test how grazing-induced changes on soil properties affect intra- and inter-specific competitive interactions between *Nardus stricta* L and

Eriophorum vaginatum L, two dominant graminoids which are known to vary in dominance in grazed and ungrazed semi-natural mountain grasslands (Grant et al., 1985; Marrs et al., 1988). Specifically, we tested the hypothesis that plant competitive interactions would be modified by grazing-induced changes in soil conditions, and consequently that each species would perform better relative to its neighbour in the soil in which it is most dominant. This was tested by growing natural occurring populations of both plant species in a glasshouse competition experiment using soils taken from a grazed *N. stricta* dominated acidic-grassland and an adjacent ungrazed area where *E. vaginatum* was more dominant. These areas formed part of a landscape-scale re-wilding experiment established in 2000 in the Yorkshire Dales, northern England. Previous work at this site (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 2) showed that cessation of sheep grazing lead to significant changes in aboveground and belowground properties, including a shift in the dominant graminoid from *N. stricta* to *E. vaginatum*, and an associated decrease in soil microbial activity and soil N availability.

4.4 Material and methods

4.4.1 Experimental design

We tested how effects of grazing on soil properties affected *N. stricta*-*E. vaginatum* interactions using a plant competition experiment combined with a plant-soil feedback approach. Whereas the ideal plant-soil feedback experiment involves cultivating soil with targeted plant species, the use of soil from habitats with known plant occurrences is common practice (Kulmatiski and Kardol, 2008). We sampled soil in December 2008 from two areas in the Ingleborough National Natural Reserve in the Yorkshire Dales National

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Park, northern England (54.18° N, 2.36° E, UK National Grid Reference Number SD 763762). One area is an acidic upland grassland dominated by *N. stricta* (Rodwell, 1992) and subjected to continuous grazing by sheep, whereas the other is an ungrazed adjacent site that was fenced-off in 2000 in order to exclude domestic herbivores (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 2 for more information about the site characteristics).

Exclusion of herbivores has resulted in an increase in the abundance of *E. vaginatum* and ericaceous shrubs, and decreases in soil microbial activity, soil N availability, and an increase in soil moisture content (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 2). We sampled soil from 10 randomly chosen points within both the grazed and ungrazed areas in order to collect sufficient material for the experiment. Soils were passed through a 2 mm mesh to remove roots and plant residues and stored at 4°C. Since our aim was to test how the effects from the contrasting soils built-up as the experiment progressed, we eliminated confounding effects caused by initial soil nutrient contents by mixing soils with sand in a 1:5 ratio. This practice is common in plant-soil experiments (Bever, 1994; Frank et al., 2003). Most soil properties including extractable inorganic N did not differ significantly in the soil-sand mixtures between the soils taken from the grazed and ungrazed areas at the beginning of the experiment (Table 4.1), except for a higher net potential NH_4^+ mineralization rate in the grazed than ungrazed soil, and a slightly higher total C content in the ungrazed than grazed soil (Table 4.1). The mixture was used to fill 1-L experimental pots (10 x 12 cm) where plants were allowed to establish.

Competitive interactions between *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* were assessed with a full-factorial design with 4 combined densities of each plant species in order to separate intra- and inter-specific components of competition. This design is commonly used

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Table 4.1: Differences in selected soil properties between soil-sand mixtures from a grazed (G^+) versus ungrazed (G^-) seminatural upland ecosystems. Cmic and Nmic = soil C and N in microbial biomass ($\text{mg kg dry soil}^{-1}$) respectively. NH_4^+ av, NH_4^+ min, NO_3^- av, NO_3^- min are ammonium and nitrate measures where av = soil extractable concentration ($\text{mg kg dry soil}^{-1}$) and min = net potential mineralization rates ($\text{mg kg dry soil}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) respectively. Csoil and Nsoil = total soil C and N (%) respectively. Analytical techniques are described in the methods section except for total soil C and N (ground soil, oven-dried at 105°C , and analysed in a Vario EL Elemental Analyser, Elementar Inc, Germany), and net mineralization rates described in Harrison and Bardgett (2010). Values are means (se).

Variable	G^+	G^-	t value (P)
Cmic	127 (13)	159 (26)	1.0 (NS)
Nmic	49 (2.5)	48 (1.4)	-0.1 (NS)
NH_4^+ av	16.0 (0.4)	16.0 (0.4)	-2.0 (\dagger)
NO_3^- av	2.1 (0.25)	1.6 (0.17)	1.5 (NS)
NH_4^+ min	1.19 (0.07)	0.26 (0.09)	-8.0 (***)
NO_3^- min	-0.15 (0.01)	-0.11 (0.01)	1.5 (NS)
Csoil	6.0 (0.15)	7.3 (0.30)	4.5 (**)
Nsoil	0.27 (0.005)	0.26 (0.006)	1.3 (NS)

NS = no significant difference, $\dagger = 0.1 \leq P \leq 0.05$, $** = P < 0.01$, $*** = P < 0.001$.

to study plant-plant competitive interactions because it overcomes many of the disadvantages present in the additive or substitution series (Snaydon, 1991; Watkinson and Freckleton, 1997; Inouye, 2001). Intact soil turves taken from the grazed and ungrazed areas, with plants of *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* respectively, were sampled on the same date as soil, and taken to Lancaster where they were placed in a glasshouse for 6 weeks. Once the plants had grown fully-green tissues, they were split into individual tillers with 2-fully developed leaves and roots. Tillers of each species were randomly assigned to 1 out of 32 combinations of the full-factorial arrangement of soil source (grazed vs ungrazed) and 4 tiller densities for each plant species (4 densities for *N. stricta* and 4 densities for *E. vaginatum*), with 5 replicates per treatment ($2 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5 = 160$). We used the following plant densities for each plant species: no plants, low density =

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2 tillers; medium density = 4 tillers; and high density = 6 tillers. Tillers were planted equidistantly, and in the case of both species mixtures, tiller position was assigned randomly. After planting, tillers were allowed to establish for another 6 weeks. During this period, unsuccessful tillers were replaced until full establishment was achieved. At this time, the experiment was allowed to run for 7 months with a 12/12 hrs light-dark cycle, a mean irradiance of 430 Wm^{-2} (std. dev. = 190 Wm^{-2}), mean average temperature of 20°C , and mean atmospheric humidity of 55 %. Experimental pots were watered every day with deionized water to reach approximately 60 % of the water holding capacity (65 % gravimetric soil content).

4.4.2 Plant measures

In late September 2009, experimental pots were harvested by cutting the shoot material. Crowns (defined as the transitional tissue between shoots and roots) and roots were separated from the soil manually and sorted by species, except for a root fraction ($0.36 \pm 0.03 \text{ g}$ per pot) which could not be assigned with certainty to any of the species, and which was not included in the analyses. All plant material was oven-dried at 70°C for 48 hours and weighed per species to determine individual tiller weight, total shoot, crown, and root biomass, and to partition of total biomass among these 3 plant components.

4.4.3 Soil measures

The soil collected after plants were harvested was passed through a 2 mm sieve and stored at 4°C until laboratory analysis took place. Soil was analysed for concentrations of extractable ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-), and for soil microbial biomass carbon

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(C) and N, and basal respiration, as a measure of microbial activity. Soil NH_4^+ content was measured by extracting 10 g of fresh soil in 1 M KCl, stirring the extracts during 1 hour in an orbital shaker, filtering them in Whatman paper No.1, and determining NH_4^+ concentration by continuous-flow colorimetry using the sodium nitroprusside reaction in a Bran and Luebbe AutoAnalyzer 3. Nitrate was measured as for NH_4^+ , but through the sulfanilamide method. Microbial biomass C and N were assayed by the chloroform (CHCl_3) fumigation extraction technique. Microbial biomass was estimated according to Vance et al. (1987) by extracting 5 g of both non-fumigated and 24-h CHCl_3 fumigated fresh soil in 0.5 M K_2SO_4 , shaking the soil-extract for 30 min in an orbital shaker, and filtering the soil extract in Whatman paper No. 1. Microbial biomass C was calculated as the difference between fumigated and non-fumigated samples after analysing the extracts for C content in a Shimadzu 5000A TOC analyser (Shimadzu Inc., Japan), and using an extraction efficiency of 0.45 (Sparling et al., 1990). Microbial biomass N was assayed by digesting the soil extracts with potassium persulfate (Cabrera and Beare, 1993) and determining N contents with flow colorimetry as described above. Microbial biomass N was calculated as the N difference between fumigated and non-fumigated soils using an extraction efficiency of 0.54 (Brookes et al., 1985). Soil basal respiration was determined following Bardgett et al. (1999b) as the production of CO_2 by 24-h incubated at 25 C of 1 g dry mass equivalent soil within sealed McCartney bottles soils. The CO_2 production after the incubation period was measured by injecting 1 mL of sample from the bottles' head-space into an ADC 225 MK3 IRGA (ADC Bioscientific Ltd., Hoddesdon, UK), and using respective blanks and CO_2 standards. Soil moisture content was standardized in all samples at 30 % for the basal respiration determinations.

4.4.4 Data analysis

4.4.4.1 Plant biomass responses

Total shoot, crown and root biomass, shoot to belowground (crown + roots) ratio, and the proportion of total biomass partitioned to shoots, roots or crowns per species, were analysed by ANOVA following two approaches. First, soil source and type of competition treatment (monocultures vs mixtures) were used as the ANOVA factors in order to evaluate how both species responded to the presence of intra- versus inter-specific competitors. Second, as a complementary approach, we explored how the species responded to the increasing levels of inter-specific competition by analysing the ANOVA models with soil source and density of the inter-specific competitor as factors. For brevity, in the results we use grazed and ungrazed to make reference to the soils from the two areas, competition effect for the type of competition (monocultures vs mixtures), and density effect for the density of the inter-specific competitor effect.

4.4.4.2 Intra- and inter-specific competition

Shoot biomass per individual tiller for each species and soil source (4 models) was analysed by the hyperbolic competition model (Mead, 1970). This model has the form:

$$w_i = w_{mi}[1 + \alpha_i(x_i + \epsilon_j x_j)]^{-1} \quad (4.1)$$

which, on a natural logarithms basis, can be expressed as:

$$\log(w_i) = \log(w_{mi}) - \log(1 + \alpha_i x_i + \alpha_{ij} x_j) \quad (4.2)$$

where w_i is the weight of an individual of species i which is modelled as a function of the density of conspecifics (x_i) and heterospecifics (x_j), w_{mi} is the mean weight of an individual of plant species i experiencing no competition, α_i , α_{ij} are parameters which measured the strength of intra- and inter-specific competition respectively, and ϵ_j can be considered as a plant species equivalence term (how many individuals of the species j are necessary to have a competitive effect equivalent to a conspecific individual) (Freckleton and Watkinson, 1997). Parameter estimates for the model were obtained by using the non-linear least squares estimation routine in the R statistical package. Effect of soil source on intra- and inter-specific competition was determined by comparing the values of the parameters for each species in the model.

4.4.5 Soil responses

We used our non-planted treatment (density of both species = 0) to test the effects that plant species had on soil properties in the grazed and ungrazed soils at the end of the experiment. Soil extractable NH_4^+ and NO_3^- , microbial biomass C and N, and basal soil respiration were analysed with ANOVA using soil source (grazed and ungrazed) and type of pot (non-planted, *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta* monocultures, and both species mixtures) as the main factors. Although we added a fixed water volume to the pots during the experiment duration, there was pot to pot variation in soil water content at the end of the experiment. Thus, final soil water content was used as a covariate for most of the analyses, except for basal respiration as moisture was standardized for this measure (see soil measures). All variables were transformed to meet the criteria of normality and variance homogeneity when necessary but results are presented for

untransformed values (means \pm se.), except in the case of the competition model. All analyses were carried out with the statistical package R for linux (R Development Core Team, 2010).

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Plant biomass responses

Shoot biomass of *E. vaginatum* in monocultures was approximately two fold greater in plants grown in grazed than ungrazed soil, but it was similar in both soils when plants experienced competition with *N. stricta* (Fig. 4.1a, soil source x competition interaction, $F_{1,108} = 45.0$, $P < 0.001$). The reduction in shoot biomass of *E. vaginatum* in response to increasing densities of *N. stricta* was stronger in grazed than ungrazed soil (see Fig. B.1, soil source x density interaction $F_{3,104} = 17.5$, $P < 0.001$). In contrast, the negative response of *N. stricta* shoot biomass to *E. vaginatum* (Fig. 4.1a, competition effect, $F_{1,111} = 25.0$, $P < 0.001$) was independent from soil source (soil source x competition interaction, $F_{1,111} = 0.5$, $P = 0.4$). *E. vaginatum* crown biomass was reduced by competition with *N. stricta* only in the grazed soil (Fig. 4.1b, soil source x competition interaction, $F_{1,107} = 8.5$, $P < 0.01$), and this reduction was particularly strong in response to low densities of *N. stricta* (Fig B.1, soil source x density interaction $F_{3,107} = 3.0$, $P < 0.01$). Competition with *E. vaginatum* likewise reduced *N. stricta* crown biomass (Fig. 4.1b, competition effect, $F_{1,108} = 24.4$, $P < 0.001$), but this response was independent of soil source (soil source x competition interaction, $F_{1,108} = 0.3$, $P = 0.5$). *Nardus stricta* crown biomass was on average 25 % greater when grown in grazed than in ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.1b, soil source effect, $F_{1,108} = 2.6$, $P < 0.01$).

Negative effects of *N. stricta* on *E. vaginatum* root biomass were greater in grazed than in ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.1c, soil source x competition interaction, $F_{1,107} = 2.0$, $P = 0.06$). Averaged across soils, competition with *E. vaginatum* decreased *N. stricta* root biomass by 40 % (competition effect, $F_{1,107} = 30.8$, $P < 0.001$), and this reduction did not differ with soil source (Fig. 4.1c, soil source x competition interaction, $F_{3,107} = 2.6$, $P = 0.1$).

Figure 4.1: Comparative indirect effects of grazing and direct effects of competition on: a) total shoot biomass, b) crown biomass, c) root biomass, d) shoot: belowground (crown+root) ratio of *Eriophorum vaginatum* (Ev) and *Nardus stricta* (Ns). Plants were grown in a glasshouse microcosm experiment with soil coming from a grazed *Nardus*-dominated acidic upland grassland (G⁺) or a *Eriophorum*-dominated ungrazed area (G⁻) in the Yorkshire Dales, England. *E. vaginatum* plants grew either in monocultures (C⁻) or with inter-specific competition by *N. stricta* (C⁺). *N. stricta* plants grew either in monocultures (C⁻) or with inter-specific competition by *E. vaginatum* (C⁺). -

4.5.2 Biomass partitioning

When competing with *N. stricta*, *E. vaginatum* allocated 15 % lower (competition effect, $F_{1,106} = 7.1$, $P < 0.01$) and 22 % greater (competition effect, $F_{1,106} = 5.9$, $P < 0.05$) biomass to shoots and crowns respectively (Fig. 4.2a). *Nardus stricta* competition did not affect biomass allocated to roots by *E. vaginatum* (competition effect, $F_{1,106} = 0.03$, $P = 0.8$), but the shoot: belowground ratio of *E. vaginatum* was reduced in competition with *N. stricta* (Fig. 4.1d, competition effect, $F_{1,106} = 6.5$, $P < 0.05$). *Eriophorum vaginatum* biomass partitioning did not respond to soil source in any case (soil source effect for proportion in: shoots, $F_{1,106} = 1.9$, $P = 0.1$; crowns, $F_{1,106} = 0.7$, $P = 0.3$; roots, $F_{1,106} = 0.06$, $P = 0.8$; and shoot: belowground ratio $F_{1,106} = 2.1$, $P = 0.1$). For *N. stricta*, biomass allocated to shoots and crowns was 13 % greater (soil effect, $F_{1,105} = 13.6$, $P < 0.001$) and 20 % lower (soil source effect, $F_{1,105} = 26.9$, $P < 0.001$), respectively, when grown on grazed compared to ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.2b). There was no effect of soil source on biomass allocation to roots (soil effect, $F_{1,105} = 0.8$, $P = 0.3$), but the shoot: belowground ratio of *N. stricta* was greater in grazed than in ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.1d, soil effect, $F_{1,105} = 13.2$, $P < 0.001$). Competition with *E. vaginatum* did not modify *N. stricta* biomass partitioning (competition effect for proportion in: shoots, $F_{1,105} = 1.2$, $P = 0.2$; crowns, $F_{1,105} = 0.3$, $P = 0.5$; roots $F_{1,105} = 1.3$, $P = 0.3$; and shoot: belowground ratio $F_{1,105} = 1.1$, $P = 0.2$).

4.5.3 Intra- and inter-specific competition

Biomass of an individual plant with no competition (represented by the parameter w_{mi}) was larger in the grazed than in the ungrazed soil for both species (Table 4.2, a ratio for $\log[w_{mi}]$ between grazed and ungrazed soils > 1 ; compare the intercepts with the

Figure 4.2: Comparative indirect effects of grazing and direct effects of competition on biomass partitioning of a) *Eriophorum vaginatum*, b) *Nardus stricta*. All legends as in Fig. 4.1 -

ordinate between Figs. 4.3a versus 4.3b for *E. vaginatum*, and 4.3c versus 4.3d) for *N. stricta*. Also, the strength of intra-specific competition (α_i) increased in grazed soil for both species (Table 4.2, ratio for α_i between grazed and ungrazed soils > 1 , Fig. 4.3b versus 4.3a; and 4.3d versus 4.3c). Unlike what happened with the previous competition parameters where the effect of soil source (ratio grazed/ungrazed) was similar for both species, the competitive effect that *N. stricta* exerted on *E. vaginatum* increased two-fold in grazed compared to ungrazed soil (Table 4.2, a ratio of 2.05 for $\epsilon_{E. vaginatum}$ between grazed and ungrazed soils; Fig. 4.3b versus 4.3a). On the other hand, the effect that *E. vaginatum* had on *N. stricta* decreased by almost a half in grazed compared to ungrazed soil (Table 4.2, a ratio < 1 for $\epsilon_{N. stricta}$ between grazed and ungrazed soils; Fig. 4.3d versus 4.3c).

4.5.4 Soil responses

Plant species effects on soil properties at the end of the experiment were assessed by comparing the non-planted treatment (density of both species = 0) with the species monocultures and both species mixtures (pot treatment effect from hereafter). There was a significant interaction between soil source and pot treatment for microbial biomass C ($F_{3,110} = 2.6$, $P < 0.05$), but only as a result of the difference between the ungrazed and grazed soils for the non-planted pot treatments (Fig. 4.4a). Despite the interaction, microbial biomass C was always higher on ungrazed soils (Fig. 4.4a, $F_{1,110} = 10.5$, $P < 0.01$) and did not differ between the pot treatments (Fig. 4.4a, $F_{3,110} = 1.8$, $P > 0.05$). On the other hand, microbial biomass N was 12 % greater in ungrazed than

Figure 4.3: Comparative indirect effects of grazing on competition of: a,b) *Eriophorum vaginatum*; c,d) *Nardus stricta*. Surface responses of plant individual biomass data fitted with the hyperbolic competition model (see equation 4.1) which is explained in the text (parameter estimates are presented in Table 4.2). Legends as in Fig. 4.1 -

Table 4.2: Indirect effects of grazing (G^+) versus herbivore exclusion (G^-) on intra-specific (α_i) and inter-specific (α_{ij} and ϵ_j) competition between *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta* as estimated by data from a microcosm experiment fitted to the hyperbolic competition model (see equation 4.1 for more details). Values are parameter estimates, their standard errors (Std. error) and values of t and associated probability (P) after fitting the model. G^+/G^- stands for the proportional effect of grazing and herbivore exclusion, so that $G^+/G^- > 1$ indicates grazing increasing competition intensity, or < 1 decreasing it.

Parameters	Parameter estimates										
	$\log(w_{mi}), (\text{mg})$			α_i			α_{ij}		ϵ_j		
	G^+	G^-	(G^+/G^-)	G^+	G^-	(G^+/G^-)	G^+	G^-	G^+	G^-	(G^+/G^-)
Species (w_i)											
<i>E. vaginatum</i>	7.20	6.40	1.13	0.12	0.08	1.50	0.25	0.08	2.08	1.02	2.05
Std. error	0.21	0.19		0.04	0.03		0.03	0.02			
t value	33.57	32.80		3.14	2.17		9.32	3.27			
P	***	***		**	*		***	**			
<i>N. stricta</i>	7.91	6.80	1.16	0.25	0.15	1.67	0.06	0.06	0.24	0.40	0.60
Std. error	0.18	0.19		0.03	0.03		0.02	0.02			
t value	41.72	34.42		6.87	4.07		2.64	2.47			
P	***	***		***	***		**	*			

* = $P < 0.05$, ** = $P < 0.01$, *** = $P < 0.001$.

grazed soil (Fig. 4.4c, $F_{1,134} = 4.0$, $P < 0.05$), but only as a result of the difference between soil sources in the non-planted pot treatments. There was no effect of soil source (Fig. 4.4b, $F_{1,110} = 1.5$, $P > 0.05$) nor pot treatment ($F_{3,110} = 1.0$, $P > 0.05$) on microbial biomass C:N ratio. Soil basal respiration was 13 % greater in grazed than ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.4d, soil source effect, $F_{1,142} = 5.0$, $P < 0.05$), and differed among pot treatments ($F_{3,142} = 5.0$, $P < 0.01$). *Post-hoc* contrasts showed that basal respiration was almost 50 % lower in non-planted than in planted pot treatments, but this measure did not vary across planted pot treatments.

At the end of the experiment, soil NH_4^+ concentration was twice as high as in grazed than ungrazed soil (Fig. 4.4e, $F_{1,141} = 60.0$; $P < 0.001$). Ammonium concentration was lower in *N. stricta* and in species mixture, in comparison to *E. vaginatum* and

non-planted pot treatments (pot type effect, $F_{3,141} = 28.0$; $P < 0.001$). Soil NH_4^+ concentration was also significantly lower on *E. vaginatum* than on non-planted pot treatments. Despite a marginally significant interaction between soil source and pot treatment ($F_{1,139} = 2.5$, $P < 0.10$), soil NO_3^- showed the same response to plant species as NH_4^+ ; i.e., lower concentrations when *N. stricta* was present in comparison with *E. vaginatum*, and lower concentrations when plants were present in comparison with non-planted pot treatments (Fig. 4.4f).

4.6 Discussion

Our objective was to evaluate the indirect effects of grazing on plant-plant interactions of dominant graminoids of semi-natural mountain grassland via modification of soil properties. We observed that competition between *N. stricta*, a grass species abundant in grazed environments (Welch, 1986), and *E. vaginatum*, a sedge species found in long-term ungrazed upland grasslands (Edgell, 1971), was modified by changes in soil resulting from grazing. Specifically, we found that the intensity of intra-specific competition for both species was greater in soils from the grazed grassland. However, the effects of grazing on inter-specific competition were species-specific: grazing increased the competitive effects of *N. stricta* on *E. vaginatum* but not vice versa. The increased intensity of intra-specific competition might be explained by an increase in plant size (Weiner, 1990; Schwinning and Weiner, 1998) as a result of higher nutrient availability on grazing-conditioned soils. This idea is supported by our measures of plant performance, soil N availability and soil microbial activity which were all greater in grazing-conditioned than in ungrazed soil at the end of the experiment. Since we eliminated differences in initial N concentration between both soils, higher final N in the soil from the grazed grassland might result

Figure 4.4: Comparison in properties between grazed and ungrazed soils from upland ecosystems and the effect of plant species on these properties: a) soil microbial biomass C, b) microbial biomass C:N ratio, c) soil microbial biomass N, d) soil basal respiration, e) soil NH_4^+ concentration, f) soil NO_3^- concentration. Soil was planted with *E. vaginatum* plants in monocultures (Ev), *N. stricta* plants in monocultures (Ns), both species under competition in a range of plant densities (Both), and soil without plants at all (None). Values are means \pm standard errors. All other legends as in Fig. 4.1 -

from grazing effects on microbial communities and microbial driven processes such as N mineralization. This increase in N availability in grazed grassland soils is supported by field measurements (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 2), and it is thought to be one of the main routes by which large herbivores indirectly influence terrestrial ecosystems (Bardgett and Wardle, 2003; Frank et al., 2003).

Indirect effects of soil conditioning by grazing on inter-specific competition were species-specific, increasing the competitive ability of *N stricta* at the expense of *E. vaginatum*. In this way, the negative influence that *N stricta* exerted on *E. vaginatum* increased two-fold, but that of *E. vaginatum* on *N stricta* decreased by half when they were grown on grazing-conditioned soil (Table 4.2). This grazing-induced asymmetric effect on interspecific competition, benefiting only the plant species that is most abundant under grazing, might be explained by the indirect influence of grazing on plant traits and soil properties. In terms of plant traits, *Nardus stricta* displayed traits positively related to competition for resources, such as increased allocation to shoots and roots in comparison to crowns (Casper and Jackson, 1997), and allocation to these traits was enhanced in grazing-conditioned soil. Hartley and Amos (1999) attributed the higher competitive ability of *N. stricta* versus *Calluna vulgaris* to its higher root length and percentage of mycorrhizae infection, which allowed *N. stricta* to exploit soil N more efficiently. Thus the enhanced expression of competitive traits might have contributed to the greater negative effect of *N. stricta* on *E. vaginatum* in these soils. The idea that *N. stricta* was more efficient exploiting soil resources is additionally supported by the finding that N concentration at the end of the experiment was lower in microcosms where *N. stricta* was present (both in monocultures and mixtures) in comparison with microcosms with *E. vaginatum* or unplanted soil. An ability to reduce soil nutrients is

considered an important trait in plant competition (Wedin and Tilman, 1993).

Although we did not condition soil with targeted plant species, our approach was broadly similar to a plant-soil feedback experiment (reviewed in Kulmatiski and Kardol, 2008) in that we used soils where our plant species showed contrasting abundances. The occurrence of positive plant-soil feedbacks in *N. stricta* has been observed in other studies (Kardol et al., 2006; Markham et al., 2008), and has been interpreted as being mediated by soil microbes, including mycorrhizal fungi, that enhance access to growth limiting nutrients, such as N and phosphorous (Kardol et al., 2006). Although we did not measure the occurrence of symbionts on plant roots, this interpretation was supported by our finding of lower N at the end of the experiment when *N. stricta* was present as stated before. Not many empirical studies have looked at the effects of plant-soil-feedback on plant competition and its components (intra- and inter-specific). In a serpentine grassland in Pennsylvania, Casper and Castelli (2007) showed how a negative plant-soil feedback translated into larger biomass of grass species when they grew in soil conditioned by heterospecific plants, but these plant-soil feedback effect was cancelled when plants experienced inter-specific competition. Since negative effects of intra- and inter-specific competition on biomass were the same independently of soil conditioning, Casper and Castelli (2007) suggested that plant species show no niche differentiation in plant-soil feedbacks and competition interactions. We observed that the larger biomass of *E. vaginatum* in grazing-conditioned soil was cancelled out when this species grew in competition with *N. stricta*. However, unlike Casper and Castelli (2007), we interpret this finding as a result of a greater ability of *N. stricta* to exploit the increased soil N availability attributed to grazing. This interpretation is supported by the fact that competition with *E. vaginatum* did not influence soil effects on *N. stricta*. As far as we

are aware, this differential effect on inter-specific competition induced by grazing is an aspect of plant-soil feedbacks that has not yet been described.

Do changes in competitive interactions between these species driven indirectly by grazing effects on soil have any significance for the dynamics of plant communities in temperate semi-natural mountain grasslands? Although artificial (i.e., it did not include important aspects of plants auto-ecology necessary to predict vegetation dynamics or changes in other soil conditions such as moisture or more plant competitors), we can use our results to make some conjectures on coexistence between our plant species. The heuristic approach in Bever et al. (1997) and Bever (2003) suggests that for plants that show strong competitive interactions to coexist, a strong negative plant soil feedback should operate. Conversely, strong competition and the occurrence of a positive feedback should lead to competitive exclusion in pair-wise competitive arenas. As said before, *N. stricta* presented a positive plant-soil feedback and its negative effect on *E. vaginatum* was increased in grazing-conditioned soil. On the other hand, *E. vaginatum* presented a negative feedback and the negative influence of *N. stricta* on it was reduced in soil where grazing was excluded. This implies that, under equilibrium conditions, *E. vaginatum* should be excluded from the grazing-induced soils by *N. stricta*; and that the later should be able to invade *E. vaginatum* dominated areas where grazing has been excluded, but in lower densities. *Eriophorum vaginatum* actually occurs in low densities in grazing-conditioned soils in the field where we collected our soils. Thus our results suggest that a non-equilibrium process such as gaps created by grazing or by heterogeneity in soil conditions promote *N. stricta*-*E. vaginatum* co-existence on the grazed acidic grassland. In this way, Ejankowski (2008) observed that experimental gap creation increased *E. vaginatum* seedling recruitment in an open bog habitat in Poland.

Changes from *N. stricta* dominated upland grasslands into more dwarf-shrub vegetation are thought to be caused by interactive effects of reduced grazing intensity and altered edaphic conditions, such as higher soil moisture content and increased surface organic matter accumulation (Ratcliffe, 1959; Edgell, 1971; Welch, 1986; Rodwell, 1992). In our field site, the reduction of *N. stricta* after grazing exclusion was also associated with an increase in soil moisture content and a decrease in N availability (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 2). Reduction of *N. stricta* after grazing cessation has been interpreted as a result of other upland plants outcompeting *N. stricta* when they are released from herbivory (Welch, 1986). Our results suggest that the reason might also lie on the effect of other environmental variables, such as soil moisture, on *N. stricta* which we did not take into account in our microcosm experiment. As an heuristic example, our model parameters are analogous as those in the Lotka-Volterra competition model (Damgaard, 1998). Apart from competition coefficients, key parameters which determine equilibrium plant species densities in the later are the intrinsic rate of growth (r) and the carrying capacity of a particular habitat (K). It seems likely that the changes in soil properties brought about by grazing exclusion are beyond *N. stricta* optimal ecological response curve (i.e., an habitat where *N. stricta* r and K are low). This view agrees with experimental results (Genney et al., 2002) which showed that *N. stricta* was not a superior competitor when its roots were not exposed to soil mineral layers (i.e., it was exposed to sub-optimal conditions).

In summary, our results showed that grazing can indirectly alter competitive interactions of plants from semi-natural mountain grasslands, and those changes might be mediated by processes regulated by soil microbial communities and other components of the soil food-web. It is well established that grazers directly influence plant competitive

interactions via selective grazing, and our results point to an additional indirect mechanisms by which grazers might alter plant-plant interactions via plant-soil feedbacks. Further studies are needed in more realistic situations to test the significance of such plant-soil feedback mechanisms as regulator of plant community dynamics in grazed ecosystems.

Chapter 5

Inter-specific competition, but not soil microbial community affects uptake of different chemical forms of nitrogen by graminoids of semi-natural, low productivity grassland

5. Inter-specific competition, but not soil microbial community affects uptake of different chemical forms of nitrogen by graminoids of semi-natural, low productivity grassland

5.1 Abstract

Interest in resource-based plant competition has increased in recent years with growing evidence that plants differ in their ability to take up different chemical forms of nitrogen (N) from soil, including organic and inorganic N. However, whether patterns of plant uptake of inorganic and organic N can be modified by other factors (such as differences in soil microbial community composition), and the consequences of this for plant competition for soil resources is less explored. Here, we report results from a plant competition microcosm experiment designed to test the hypothesis that soil microbial communities from areas of differing grazing management can modify N uptake patterns and N uptake competition in two graminoids. This was done by inoculating sterilised soil with contrasting microbial communities taken from long-term grazed and ungrazed grasslands, combined with the addition of ^{15}N labelled ammonium and dual ^{13}C , ^{15}N labelled glycine, to test for effects of soil microbes and plant competition on isotopic enrichment of plant tissue. The species used were *Eriophorum vaginatum* and *Nardus stricta*, which are common graminoids of nutrient-poor, acidic semi-natural grasslands

with differential responses to long-term grazing. We found that the different microbial communities had no effect on N uptake of either N form by these graminoids, which might suggest functional equivalence of the two microbial communities on N uptake. However, the two species differed in their preference of the N forms, *E. vaginatum* took up more organic N than did *N. stricta*, which is consistent with its field dominance in soils with a higher proportion of organic to inorganic N. In accordance with the results on plant biomass, *N. stricta*, the superior competitor, altered *E. vaginatum* N uptake patterns, reducing the proportion of organic N taken up by the later, thus increasing niche overlap in N usage. Whereas local abundances of these species in semi-natural low productivity grasslands are mainly controlled by gradients in grazing and soil moisture content, our results suggest that other soil properties such as proportion of organic N in the dissolved N pool can play a role in determining local abundances as well. Additionally, our results suggest that observed coexistence of these species in the field is not based on resource complementarity mechanisms so that other mechanisms based on non-equilibrium dynamics (such as disturbance) or soil heterogeneity might operate in order to maintain coexistence of these two plant species.

5.2 Keywords

^{15}N , ^{13}C , plant nitrogen uptake, organic nitrogen, plant competition, plant species coexistence, uplands, soil amino acids.

5.3 Introduction

Plants' ability to directly take up organic nitrogen (ON) forms is spread across a broad range of plant taxa from such contrasting habitats, including tropical and temperate forests, arctic tundra, shrublands, and grasslands (Lipson et al., 1999; Schimel and Bennett, 2004; Jones et al., 2005). Besides questioning previous assumptions on the nitrogen (N) cycle (Schimel and Bennett, 2004), it has been proposed that this ability for plants to take up ON might constitute an important mechanism regulating plant species competition (Lipson et al., 1999; McKane et al., 2002; Harrison et al., 2007; Hill et al., 2011). For instance, if plants species show differential N uptake preferences for ON or inorganic N (IN), niche overlap and competition intensity could decrease (McKane et al., 2002). Since the importance of ON increases as primary productivity decreases (Schimel and Bennett, 2004; Farrell et al., 2011), there might be some degree of niche differentiation in N use among plants that exhibit contrasting abundances across environmental gradients (Weigelt et al., 2005). However, studies on plant N chemical form uptake have shown conflicting results, with plant species from different habitats displaying preference for one N form (McKane et al., 2002; Kahmen et al., 2006), or no preference at all (Harrison et al., 2007, 2008; Paungfoo-Lonhienne et al., 2008). Whereas no preference for N chemical forms among plants that differ in habitat or plant traits might suggest weak niche differentiation, other factors could alter uptake of N chemical forms among different plant species. Inter-specific competition (Miller et al., 2007; Ashton et al., 2008, 2010) and soil microbes (Kaye and Hart, 1997; Dunn et al., 2006) are some of these factors still poorly explored, but could shed light on plant species coexistence through their effects on plant resource competition. The role of plant competition has recently

been addressed (Miller et al., 2007), but little is known about how soil microbes affect plant N uptake preferences (Dunn et al., 2006), despite the fact that microbes are key agents in N cycling.

A key factor in grasslands that is known to strongly modify microbial communities and nutrient cycling is grazing by large herbivores, which in turn can feedback to influence plant species performance and competition (Bardgett et al., 1997; Ritchie et al., 1998; Hamilton III and Frank, 2001; Bardgett and Wardle, 2003; Sørensen et al., 2008a). For instance, Frank et al. (2003) attributed increased performance of a dominant temperate grass species in Yellowstone National Park, USA, to changes in soil microbial communities (particularly mycorrhizal fungi) induced by grazing by large herbivores, which might have allowed plants to have improved access to soil nutrients. Similarly, Medina-Roldán et al. (*in review-b*) (see Chapter 4) found that grazing-induced changes on soil properties, especially higher microbial activity and N availability, in semi-natural, acid grasslands increased the competitive ability of *Nardus stricta*, which could contribute, in part, to its dominance in grazed grassland. Such observations point towards a role of grazing effects on soil microbes in mediating plant competition for soil resources, including ON and IN, either by modifying plant niche overlap (Reynolds et al., 2003), or by modifying rates of nutrient cycling.

Here, we report on a glasshouse experiment that was designed to test how grazing induced changes in soil microbial communities modify N uptake patterns for ON and IN of two dominant graminoids of semi-natural, acidic grassland that show differential responses to grazing, namely *Eriophorum vaginatum* and *N. stricta*. We also tested how patterns of ON and IN uptake by these two graminoids were affected by competitive

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interactions of these two species. Specifically, we tested three hypotheses. First, we hypothesized that the soil microbial community of grazed grassland, which was found to be more metabolically active in previous studies (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a,b*; see Chapters 3 and 4), would facilitate increased N uptake in both plant species, although the increase would be larger for *N. stricta* due to its greater competitive ability. Second, in terms of uptake patterns of ON and IN, we hypothesised that *E. vaginatum* would show a greater preference for ON than *N. stricta*, since the former is known to grow in soils with higher proportion of ON to IN (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 3). Finally, we hypothesised that, when in competition, *N. stricta* would alter the N uptake patterns of *E. vaginatum* because of its higher competitive ability. These hypotheses were tested in a plant competition glasshouse experiment, using soil inoculum from grazed and ungrazed semi-natural grasslands previously shown to differ in soil biological properties, and the use of ^{15}N labelled IN and dual-labelled ^{15}N - ^{13}C amino acids to measure how experimental treatments affected the uptake of N compounds by the two plant species.

5.4 Material and methods

5.4.1 Experimental design

5.4.1.1 Soil substratum and inoculum preparation

Our study area is located in the Ingleborough National Nature Reserve, Yorkshire Dales, northern England (54.18° N, 2.36° E, UK National Grid Reference Number SD 763762). This area is part of a landscape re-wilding experiment where acidic grassland dominated by *N. stricta*, *Agrostis capillaris* and *Festuca spp.*, and which is subjected to continuous

sheep grazing, has been fenced-off since 2000 in order to restore the grassland biodiversity. Re-wilding has led to dominance of the dwarf-shrub *Calluna vulgaris* and the graminoid *E. vaginatum*, and concomitant changes in soil properties including reductions in N availability, soil microbial activity and the ratio of IN to ON in comparison with the adjacent grazed grassland (Medina-Roldán *in review-a*, see Chapter 3).

Soils were collected from the grazed and adjacent re-wilding areas by digging a number of holes in each of two areas with contrasting grazing management (grazing and ungrazed) on July 2010 to make a composite sample per area. Since these two areas differed in a number of soil biological properties, including N availability (Medina-Roldán *in review-a*, see Chapter 3), the substratum for growing plants (referred simply as soil) was prepared by mixing both soils together - thereby excluding effects due to initial N differences between soils - , and mixing them with sand in a 1:5 ratio. Then, this composite soil sample was sterilised by autoclaving, and subsequently inoculated with a soil suspension taken from each of the grazed and ungrazed grasslands in order to isolate effects due exclusively to differences in soil microbial communities and small organisms in the soil food web. Autoclaving is known to modify soil biogeochemical properties causing a large increase in dissolved organic matter. However, to partially overcome these problem, we first air-dried soil before sterilisation, since autoclaving of dry samples is known to minimize impacts on soil properties (Salonius et al., 1967). We found that autoclaving increased soil concentrations of dissolved organic carbon (DOC), but it did not affect DON concentrations, microbial biomass C and N, or soil basal respiration in comparison with non-autoclaved soil (Table 5.1). Additionally, a comparison between autoclaved and non-autoclaved soils showed that autoclaving did not modify the outcome of plant competition (Fig. 5.1). We used 250 g of autoclaved soil to fill up

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Table 5.1: Differences in selected soil properties between air-dried-autoclaved (S) versus air-dried-non-autoclaved (NS) soil-sand mixtures. Cmic and Nmic = soil C and N in microbial biomass (mg kg dry soil⁻¹) respectively. DOC and DON are dissolved organic C and N respectively (mg kg dry soil⁻¹). Basresp = soil microbial basal respiration ($\mu\text{L CO}_2 \text{ kg dry soil}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$). $|t|$ = absolute value for the Welch Two Sample t-test and its associated probability (P). $n = 3$. Values are means (se).

Soil variable	NS	S	$ t $	P
Cmic	0.45 (0.45)	16.1 (16)	0.7	> 0.50
Nmic	17 (1.9)	14 (8.2)	0.2	> 0.80
DOC	350 (24)	587 (174)	36.0	< 0.001 ***
DON	4.5 (0.9)	15.0 (4.4)	2.3	> 0.10
Basresp	2.5 (0.8)	2.9 (0.7)	0.3	> 0.70

plastic pots (10 cm diameter, 9.5 cm height), which were set to 65 % of soil water holding capacity (40 %) to be inoculated with microbial communities and seeded as described below.

Inoculum from each grazed and ungrazed soils was prepared by firstly passing fresh soil from each grassland through a 2 mm sieve to eliminate plant residues, and storing it at 4°C until it was to be used to inoculate the microcosms. Previous experiments vary largely in terms of the criteria they use to prepare soil inoculum (Griffiths et al., 2001; Kardol et al., 2007; Wertz et al., 2007; Hol et al., 2010). Ours was prepared by mixing fresh soil with a sterile weak Ringer solution, following the approach of Griffiths et al. (2001) in a 0.5:1 ratio (w/v). Microcosms were inoculated with 30 mL of inoculum assigned randomly from either grazed or ungrazed soils. After inoculation, plants were immediately planted (see below).

5.4.1.2 Plant species establishment and competition treatments

We sampled plant turves from *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* during October 2009 and put them in a glasshouse at Lancaster University. Turves were put outdoors for 3 weeks and then reallocated to the glasshouse in late January in order to induce flowering (Ian Dodd pers. comm.). Plant seeds from both species were collected during March and April 2010. A pilot assay indicated that the germination rate of *N. stricta* was low; hence, we used a 3-week low temperature (at 4 °C) stratification period to enhance germination, as suggested by Kissling et al. (2006). Two week old seedlings of *N. stricta* were transferred into the microcosms in early September 2010 just after soil inoculation, and *E. vaginatum* seeds were planted 1 week after. Since it was shown that competition between these two species occurs even in low densities (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review*-b, Chapter 4), we used 2 plant individuals in a substitution design. Inoculated microcosms were assigned randomly to the following competition treatments: *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* monocultures, and an inter-specific competition treatment with one individual of each species (see next section for number of replicates). Plants were allowed to grow for another 8 weeks. After this period, we applied the ¹⁵N labelling treatments in order to test for the influence of inter-specific competition on the uptake of ON and IN by these plant species, and how patterns of N uptake were affected by the different microbial communities.

5.4.1.3 ¹⁵N and ¹³C labelling, and microcosms harvest

Plant N uptake was assessed by tracking ¹⁵N and ¹³C labelled N compounds into plant tissues following the method described by Weigelt et al. (2005). In this method, plant

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preferences for IN and ON are resolved by using mixtures of N compounds where only one member in the mixture is either ^{15}N labelled (inorganic N) or dual ^{13}C - ^{15}N labelled (organic N). In our case, we used only glycine (Gly) and NH_4^+ . Discussions on limitations and strengths of the technique can be found elsewhere (Streeter et al., 2000; Näsholm et al., 2009a; Rasmussen and Kuzyakov, 2009). Three N solutions (labelled $\text{NH}_4^+ = ^{15}\text{N}$ -98 %, dual labelled Gly = ^{13}C 98 %; ^{15}N 98 %, CK Gas Products Ltd.) containing both N compounds in equal N molarities were used: 1) $^{15}\text{NH}_4^+$ + unlabelled Gly; 2) dual-labelled Gly + unlabelled NH_4^+ ; and 3) both Gly + NH_4^+ unlabelled as a control. Each solution was randomly assigned to the microcosms where a combination of inoculum source and competition treatments had already been applied. Each inoculum source x competition x labelled N solution combination had 4 replicates ($N = 72$). A treatment with distilled water was included to determine isotopic natural abundances. Nitrogen solutions were applied adding $10 \mu\text{g N g dry soil}^{-1}$ in 5-aliqouts of 1 mL evenly distributed on microcosms using a glass syringe with a 152 mm needle with sealed tip and 4 side ports. A short-term labeling period of 48 hrs was used in order to minimize effects on results of amino acid turnover and ^{15}N dilution (Jones et al., 2005; Weigelt et al., 2005). Shoot biomass for each species was oven-dried at 70°C for 48 hrs and weighed. Roots were separated from the soil, rinsed in 0.5 M CaCl_2 , and thoroughly washed under tap water to eliminate external isotopic traces and oven-dried and weighed as for shoot biomass.

5.4.2 Laboratory assays

Dried shoot and root biomass samples were ground in a ball-mill and sent to the Stable Light Isotope Facility in the University of Bradford, United Kingdom, for analysis of elemental C and N, and isotopic mass ratio of $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ and $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ in an Thermo Finnigan Delta Plus XL continuous flow mass spectrometer equipped with a Flash EA 1112 elemental analyser. Following Näsholm et al. (2000), we calculated isotopic enrichment (also called molar excess) in plant tissue as:

$$\text{molar excess} = [A * (\text{conc}/100) * DW * F] / DW \quad (5.1)$$

where conc = N or C content in plant tissue (%), DW is dry plant biomass and F is the reciprocal of the molar mass of the isotopic species in question (either ^{15}N or ^{13}C). In the previous formula A is:

$$A = (\text{atm}\%_{\text{enriched}} - \text{atm}\%_{\text{control}}) / 100 \quad (5.2)$$

this is the difference in atm % between the enriched N solutions and the distilled water treatment (Fisher et al., 1979).

Soil collected after harvest was stored at 4°C until laboratory analysis took place. We determined soil microbial biomass C and N using the fumigation extraction technique (Vance et al., 1987). Five g of fresh soil were extracted in 0.5 M K_2SO_4 by shaking the soil-extract for 30 min in an orbital shaker and filtering the soil extract in Whatman paper No. 1. Microbial biomass C was calculated as the difference between fumigated and non-fumigated soils after analysing the extracts for C concentration in a Shimadzu 5000A

TOC analyser (Shimadzu Inc., Japan), and using an extraction efficiency of 0.45 (Sparling et al., 1990). Microbial biomass N was assayed by digesting the soil extracts with potassium persulfate (Cabrera and Beare, 1993), and N concentration was determined by using continuous-flow colorimetry in a Bran and Luebbe AutoAnalyzer 3. Microbial biomass N was calculated as the difference in N between fumigated and non-fumigated soils using an extraction efficiency of 0.54 (Brookes et al., 1985).

5.4.3 Statistical analysis

Soil collected after harvest was stored at 4 °C until laboratory analysis took place. We determined soil microbial biomass C and N using the fumigation extraction technique (Vance et al., 1987). Five g of fresh soil were extracted in 0.5 M K₂SO₄ by shaking the soil-extract for 30 min in an orbital shaker and filtering the soil extract in Whatman paper No. 1. Microbial biomass C was calculated as the difference between fumigated and non-fumigated soils after analysing the extracts for C concentration in a Shimadzu 5000A TOC analyser (Shimadzu Inc., Japan), and using an extraction efficiency of 0.45 (Sparling et al., 1990). Microbial biomass N was assayed by digesting the soil extracts with potassium persulfate (Cabrera and Beare, 1993), and N concentration was determined by using continuous-flow colorimetry in a Bran and Luebbe AutoAnalyzer 3. Microbial biomass N was calculated as the difference in N between fumigated and non-fumigated soils using an extraction efficiency of 0.54 (Brookes et al., 1985).

5.5 Results

5.5.1 Plant biomass

At the end of the experiment, inter-specific competition with *N. stricta* caused an 85 % reduction in *E. vaginatum* shoot biomass ($F_{1,47} = 50.0$, $P < 0.001$), and a 63 % decrease in its root biomass ($F_{1,43} = 26.0$, $P < 0.001$) in comparison with monocultures (Fig. 5.1a,c). There was a weakly significant inoculum source x competition interaction for *E. vaginatum* root biomass ($F_{1,43} = 4.5$, $P = 0.04$), in that the negative effect of inter-specific competition on this measure was slightly stronger in the ungrazed soil (Fig. 5.1c). No effects of soil microbial communities were detected for either shoot ($F_{1,47} = 0.06$, $P > 0.8$) or root biomass ($F_{1,43} = 0.5$, $P > 0.5$) of *E. vaginatum*, except for the already described interaction for roots. In contrast, *N. stricta* was not affected by inter-specific competition either in terms of shoot ($F_{1,50} = 0.004$, $P > 0.9$) or root biomass ($F_{1,48} = 0.9$, $P > 0.4$), and inoculum source had no influence on the growth of this species either ($F_{1,50} = 1.6$, $P > 0.2$; $F_{1,48} = 0.6$, $P > 0.4$ for shoot and root biomass respectively, Fig. 5.1b,d).

5.5.2 Plant N uptake

Linear regressions of log transformed data of ^{13}C against ^{15}N molar excess in the glycine (Gly) labelled treatment showed that it was likely that both species took up intact organic N (*E. vaginatum* shoots: $F_{1,10} = 19.0$, $P < 0.01$; roots: $F_{1,8} = 38.5$, $P < 0.001$; *N. stricta* shoots: $F_{1,10} = 5.5$, $P < 0.05$; roots: $F_{1,10} = 4.0$, $P = 0.07$; Fig. 5.2). There was no evidence of ^{13}C or ^{15}N enrichment in either species in the unlabelled control, suggesting that contamination of plant tissue through incorporation of respired ^{13}C was negligible (Figs. 5.3 and 5.4). Soil microbial communities from grazed or

Figure 5.1: Effect of microbial inoculum from a grazed *Nardus*-dominated acidic semi-natural grassland (G^+) and a *Eriophorum*-dominated ungrazed grassland (G^-), and inter-specific competition on: (a) *E. vaginatum* shoot biomass; (b) *N. stricta* shoot biomass; (c) *E. vaginatum* root biomass; and (d) *N. stricta* root biomass. Data show the effects of inter-specific competition when both plants were grown without (C^-) or with (C^+) inter-specific competition. Gray bars (NA) indicate the effect of competition on each species biomass component on non-inoculated soils. Values are means \pm se. -

ungrazed soils did not have a significant effect on any of the root or shoot isotopic enrichment variables (^{15}N or ^{13}C) for either species. On the other hand, a marginal species (within competition) x labelled N solution interaction for ^{15}N enrichment in shoot biomass ($F_{2,34} = 3.0$, $P = 0.06$) provided evidence that our plant species displayed different N uptake preferences. Thus, enrichment of *E. vaginatum* shoots with ^{15}N was 63 % greater when supplied with labelled glycine (Gly) than NH_4^+ (Fig. 5.3a), indicating a preference for ON over IN source by this species. The opposite was true for *N. stricta*, in that ^{15}N enrichment of shoot tissue of this species was 66 % greater when supplied with labelled NH_4^+ than Gly (Fig. 5.4a), suggesting a preference for IN over ON.

With respect to the effects of inter-specific competition on N compounds uptake, shoot ^{13}C enrichment was 35 % less (averaged across plant species) in plant mixtures than in monocultures in the Gly treatment ($F_{1,15} = 6.2$, $P < 0.05$; Figs. 5.3c,d; and 5.4c,d). Inter-specific competition also reduced shoot ^{15}N enrichment by 27 % (averaged across species and N sources) in comparison with monocultures (marginally significant effect: $F_{1,34} = 3.1$, $P = 0.08$; Figs. 5.3a,b; and 5.4a,b). However, inter-specific competition did not affect either ^{13}C ($F_{1,15} = 1.8$, $P = 0.19$; Figs. 5.3g,h; and 5.4g,h), or ^{15}N enrichment in roots ($F_{1,37} = 1.5$, $P = 0.22$; Figs. 5.3e,f; and 5.4e,f) for either species. When N uptake preference per species was expressed as total ^{15}N enrichment in shoots, inter-specific competition did not alter N uptake preferences of either species (competition x labelled N solution interaction, $F_{1,34} = 0.33$, $P = 0.56$). However, when preference was expressed as proportion of ^{15}N enrichment of a single compound in relation to total enrichment in shoots (e.g., preference for NH_4^+ : $\text{mol excess NH}_4^+ / [\text{mol excess Gly} + \text{mol excess NH}_4^+]$), inter-specific competition did affect N preferences of *E. vaginatum*,

Figure 5.2: Regression analysis and parameter estimates of log transformed data of ^{15}N against ^{13}C mol excess for shoot (a) and root (b) biomass of plants treated with dual-labelled (^{13}C and ^{15}N) glycine (Gly) + unlabelled NH_4^+ .

Figure 5.3: Effects of microbial inoculum source (G^+ vs G^-) and inter-specific competition on *Eriophorum vaginatum* ^{15}N and ^{13}C isotopic enrichment (expressed as molar excess) of: (a-d) shoot; and (e-h) root biomass. Data show the effects of inter-specific competition when plants were grown without (left panels) or with inter-specific competition (right panels) after applying glycine-ammonium solutions with isotopic dual-labelled (^{13}C and ^{15}N) glycine (Gly), ^{15}N -labelled NH_4^+ (Din) or both compounds unlabelled (None). Values are means \pm se. Legends as in Fig. 5.1. 112

Figure 5.4: Effects of microbial inoculum source (G^+ vs G^-) and inter-specific competition on *Nardus stricta* ^{15}N and ^{13}C isotopic enrichment (expressed as molar excess) of: (a-d) shoot; and (e-h) root biomass. Data show the effects of inter-specific competition when plants were grown without (left panels) or with (right panels) inter-specific competition after applying glycine-ammonium solutions with isotopic dual-labelled (^{13}C and ^{15}N) glycine (Gly), ^{15}N -labelled NH_4^+ (Din) or both compounds unlabelled (None). Values are means \pm se. Legends as in Fig. 5.1. -

but not of *N. stricta* (Fig. 5.5). More precisely, inter-specific competition with *N. stricta* reduced the proportion of ON taken-up by *E. vaginatum* in comparison with *E. vaginatum* monocultures (Fig. 5.5a,b).

Figure 5.5: Effects of inter-specific competition on proportional N uptake (based on shoot ^{15}N mol excess) of glycine (Gly) vs NH_4^+ (Din) for *E. vaginatum* (a,b) and *N. stricta* (c,d). Left and right panels correspond to plants without or with inter-specific competition respectively -

5.5.3 Soil microbial properties

There were no differences between grazed and ungrazed inoculated soils in microbial properties, namely microbial biomass C ($F_{1,70} = 0.007$, $P > 0.90$), N ($F_{1,70} = 0.06$, $P > 0.70$), and C:N ratio ($F_{1,66} = 0.15$, $P > 0.70$) (Fig. 5.6). Also, none of these soil microbial variables responded to plant species identity, either as monocultures or when both plants grew in competition ($F_{1,70} = 0.15$, $P > 0.80$; $F_{1,70} = 0.6$, $P > 0.50$; and $F_{1,66} = 0.75$, $P > 0.70$, for soil microbial C, N and C:N ratio, respectively).

5.6 Discussion

We investigated how grazing-induced differences in microbial communities and plant competitive interactions influenced patterns of organic (ON) and inorganic (IN) N uptake by the graminoids *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta* of semi-natural, low productivity grasslands. Abundances of these two plant species in semi-natural grasslands vary across gradients of grazing and soil properties (Ratcliffe, 1959; Edgell, 1971; Grant et al., 1985; Welch, 1986; Rodwell, 1992), with *E. vaginatum* being more abundant under ungrazed conditions, and higher soil moisture contents (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 3); and *N. stricta* being dominant in grazed grasslands. Furthermore, the ratio of ON to IN is higher in soils where *E. vaginatum* is more abundant (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 3). Therefore, we predicted that these two plant species would show different N uptake preference; with *E. vaginatum* showing a preference for ON over IN, and *N. stricta* showing the opposite. Consistent with this notion, we observed that *E. vaginatum* displayed greater uptake of ON than *N. stricta*, even when both N chemical forms were added in similar concentrations, and *N. stricta* showed a higher preference for

Figure 5.6: Effects of microbial inoculum source (G⁺ vs G⁻) and pot-type (a proxy for plant species) on: (a) soil microbial biomass C; (b) soil microbial biomass N; and (c) microbial biomass C:N ratio. Soils were planted with *E. vaginatum* plants in monocultures (Ev), *N. stricta* plants in monocultures (Ns), and both species under competition (Both). Values are means \pm se. Legends as in Fig. 5.1. -

IN. Preferential use of ON over IN by *E. vaginatum* has been shown elsewhere (Chapin III et al., 1993). However, in contrast to Weigelt et al. (2005) who showed that *N. stricta* preferred to uptake the amino acid serine over IN, we found that this species showed a preference for IN over glycine. However, other studies, done both as single species in glasshouse conditions (Harrison et al., 2008) and in mixed communities *in situ* (Harrison et al., 2007) have not detected greater ON utilization over IN by this grass species. Also, the greater capacity of *N. stricta* to uptake IN compared to *E. vaginatum* in our study is consistent with the findings of Havill et al. (1974), who found a greater nitrate reductase activity in *N. stricta* in response to the addition of nitrate than for *E. vaginatum*. Previous studies have interpreted differentiation in uptake of chemical forms of N as a mechanism for plant species local coexistence (McKane et al., 1990, 2002; Kahmen et al., 2006). Unlike those studies, we interpret differentiation in preferences for chemical forms of N in our plant species as a result of their differentiation in occurrence along gradients of grazing and soil properties (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 3). Thus, contrasting abundances of our species in the field seem to be determined mainly by their inter-specific differences to soil properties (Edgell, 1971; Wein, 1973; Rodwell, 1992), and grazing resistance (Grant et al., 1985; Welch, 1986; Hartley and Amos, 1999; Medina-Roldán and Bardgett, 2011, see Chapter 2).

Our main hypothesis was that soil microbial communities from grazed and ungrazed grassland would influence the uptake preferences for inorganic (IN) and organic N (ON) by *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*. As already stated, these two graminoids are common in these upland habitats where they exhibit a contrasting response to grazing (*N. stricta* increases and *E. vaginatum* decreases) and different plant traits related to competition for soil resources (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-b*, Chapter 4). Given these differences

and the extent that grazing is known to influence the biomass, activity and structure of soil microbial communities (Bardgett et al., 1997; Bardgett and Wardle, 2003; Frank et al., 2003; Sørensen et al., 2008a), we hypothesised that soil microbial communities could alter patterns of N uptake by these species. However, despite reported differences in the biomass and activity of soil microbial communities (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a,b*; Chapter 3), we found that inoculating soils with microbial inocula from the ungrazed and grazed areas did not affect plant N uptake of either plant species. We know that soil microbes grew after soil inoculation, as evidenced by the soil microbial biomass C and N values at the end of the experiment, but microbial biomass C was half than that previously found in the field (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-a*, Chapter 3). Thus, the lack of effect of soil microbes from different habitats on plant N uptake observed here might have resulted from the small size of the microbial community in inoculated microcosms, or, alternatively, it might suggest that microbial communities of grazed and ungrazed grasslands were functionally equivalent (Wertz et al., 2006, 2007) with respect to their effect of plant N uptake. This latter notion is broadly consistent with Harrison et al. (2008), who found no difference in uptake of chemical forms of N, both organic and inorganic, by the soil microbial biomass of soils influenced by a range of plant species with contrasting life histories. However, Dunn et al. (2006) directly manipulated soil microbial properties through the addition of glucose and found that an increase in microbial activity, after glucose addition, altered patterns of ON and IN uptake in other upland grass species. However, as we did not measure ^{15}N enrichment in the microbial biomass, we are not able to distinguish between these two interpretations, i.e., whether the lack of effect is due to small size of the microbial community or whether it reflects functional equivalence.

Finally, we also tested how inter-specific competition affected N uptake patterns. Specifically, we expected that *N. stricta* would affect *E. vaginatum* N uptake more than it would be affected. We based this hypothesis on the fact that *N. stricta* exhibited traits related to higher competitive ability and it had a greater negative effect on *E. vaginatum* biomass in a previous study (Medina-Roldán et al. *in review-b*, Chapter 4). Mirroring the results on shoot and root biomass, *N. stricta* altered N uptake patterns of *E. vaginatum*, but it was not affected by inter-specific competition. The main effect of *N. stricta* competition was to reduce proportional uptake of ON (proportion of ON with respect to total uptake of ON plus IN found in shoots) by *E. vaginatum*, therefore increasing its proportional uptake of IN. Since *N. stricta* main N source was IN, alteration of *E. vaginatum* N uptake patterns by *N. stricta* is likely to have increased resource overlap in IN of these plant species. Ashton et al. (2010) found that the superior competitor in an alpine grassland switched to different N forms (higher plasticity) when competing with other plant species, thus increasing resource complementarity. They hypothesised that this plasticity could reduce resource niche overlap, therefore promoting plant coexistence in their alpine ecosystem. Unlike Ashton et al. (2010), we did not observe the superior competitor to display plasticity in N forms uptake, but to cause a switch in N use by the inferior competitor which might have increased N niche overlap. Increase N niche overlap and those results on plant competition described in Medina-Roldán et al. (*in review-b*, Chapter 4) suggest that the observed co-existence between *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* in a large range of conditions in semi-natural mountain grasslands (Chadwick, 1960; Wein, 1973) must be based on mechanisms others than those which reduce intensity of competition and slow down competitive exclusion. Such other mechanisms might rely on non-equilibrium dynamics caused by herbivores gap creation or heterogeneity in soil

conditions.

In summary, we found that *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*, two dominant graminoids of semi-natural, low productivity grassland, differ in their patterns of inorganic and organic N uptake, and that this might be related to the relative availabilities of ON and IN in the habitats where these species dominate. Specifically, we found that *E. vaginatum* takes up more organic than inorganic N, whereas the opposite is true for *N. stricta*. Furthermore, we found that inter-specific competition with *N. stricta* increased the proportional usage of inorganic N in *E. vaginatum*, the weaker competitor, increasing species resource overlap and likely intensity of competition. This last finding suggests that coexistence of these plant species in semi-natural mountain habitats is unlikely to be based on mechanisms which promote resource use complementarity. We hypothesise that coexistence in these species might rather be based on non-equilibrium mechanisms such as disturbance and gap creation caused by herbivores or heterogeneity in soil conditions.

Chapter 6

General Discussion

6. General Discussion

6.1 Summary

Grazing by large herbivores shows an increasing trend as a land use practice at a global scale, raising concerns over herbivore effects on ecological processes, particularly in highly vulnerable ecosystems such as British semi-natural mountain grasslands. This, together with local changes in grazing management expected within the UK, makes it important to estimate ecosystem-level consequences of grazing by large herbivores, including soil processes, and the mechanism involved to better understand trade-offs incurred by this management practice in ecosystem services. Thus, the general aim of this thesis was to assess grazing impacts on soil processes and soil microbial communities in temperate, poor-nutrient semi-natural grasslands in northern England, and the consequences on these impacts on plant-plant interactions for key plant species in these ecosystems. I addressed this main research question by setting up four specific objectives (Chapter 1) which combined field and microcosm experiments. Overall, my results show that grazing has important consequences on soil nutrient dynamics and soil properties, and that grazing might have important indirect consequences for plant species competition in semi-natural mountain grasslands. Next, I discuss these main findings into more detail, together with their significance in terms of the structure of semi-natural mountain grasslands.

6.2 Direct effects of grazing on soil properties in poor-nutrient semi-natural grasslands

First of all, I contrasted soil properties related to carbon and nitrogen cycling between continuously-grazed and long-term grazing excluded acidic grasslands in a grazing-cessation project in the Yorkshire Dales (Chapter 2). This was done to determine effects of different grazing management practices on selected soil properties in poor-nutrient semi-mountain grasslands typical of northern England (specific objective 1, see Chapter 1). For this field experiment, I hypothesised that the increase in dwarf-shrubs brought about by grazing exclusion would be associated with a slowing-down in N and C cycling. Effectively, once seasonal variability was taken into account, the field experiment showed that grazing cessation was characterised by reductions in rates of N mineralisation and microbial activity in comparison with continuously-grazed grasslands. Additionally, grazing cessation was related to microbial communities with lower microbial biomass N. These differences in belowground biological properties between grazing regimes concurred with an increase in dwarf-shrubs, a decrease in graminoids, and an increase in the proportion of biomass found in the litter as a result of grazing cessation.

Faster nutrient cycling as a consequence of increase in graminoids abundance in expense of dwarf-shrubs observed here is consistent with results in poor-nutrient heathlands where the replacement of dwarf-shrubs by grasses increases nutrient cycling (Aerts, 1989; van Vuuren et al., 1992; Berendse, 1998). In such poor-nutrient heathlands, increases in cover of grasses like *Molinia cerulea* and *Deschampsia flexuosa* are typically associated with increases in soil nutrient availability (Berendse, 1998). Such increase in nutrient cycling in response to higher graminoid abundance has been explained on the basis of dif-

6.2 Direct effects of grazing on soil properties in poor-nutrient semi-natural grasslands

ferences in plant traits related to nutrient conservation and turnover between graminoids and dwarf-shrubs. In this way, lower nutrient use efficiency, nutrient resorption and leaf life span in graminoids in comparison to dwarf-shrubs is related to production of higher quality litter which could, in turn, positively affect microbial-mediated litter decomposition, thus increasing nutrient cycling (Aerts, 1996; Berendse, 1998; Garnier and Aronson, 1998).

I did not measure differences in plant functional traits related to nutrient use efficiency (as described above) between continuously-grazed and ungrazed areas in the field experiment directly. However, my results of higher microbial activity, N mineralization, microbial biomass N, and higher dissolved inorganic N (DIN) to dissolved organic N (DON) ratio in the continuously-grazed area suggest that the well-known differences in traits among plant functional groups affecting litter decomposition are a plausible explanation for the effects of grazing on soil properties. This was true even against the high backdrop noise produced by inter-annual variability. Additional evidence that grazing increased rates of nutrient cycling through its effects on plant functional groups composition comes from the fact that stocking rates in the continuously-grazed area are relatively low, in the order of 4 ewes ha⁻¹ during the growing season and 1.5 ewes ha⁻¹ during the season of low plant productivity (Colin Newlands, Natural England, *pers. comm.*), so that input of N-enriched animal excreta might be low (note that estimates of N and other nutrient inputs by herbivores and their spatial variability in the field are scarce, Sheldrick et al., 2003; Jewell et al., 2007). Furthermore, although grazing cessation increased gravimetric soil moisture content slightly (20 % in relation to continuously-grazed grasslands on average), both areas showed very high soil moisture content values (above 450 %), and grazing management did not affect water table depth. These facts

6.3 Plant defoliation recreates observed direct effects of grazing, differences in plant traits are less important

make it improbable that differences in soil properties between the continuously-grazed and the ungrazed areas were due entirely to their differences in hydrological properties affecting microbial processes (Fenchel et al., 1998).

It has been suggested that it is more likely for grazing to increase soil nutrient cycling in rich-nutrient environments (Bardgett et al., 2003; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010), since these conditions are associated more often with plant compensatory responses to herbivory and plant grazing tolerance strategies (Maschinski and Whitham, 1989, but see Wise and Abrahamson 2005). Despite low-productivity of semi-natural mountain grasslands, continuous grazing increased N mineralization and soil microbial activity in comparison with exclusion of grazing in the field. Since grazing cessation promotes the dominance of dwarf-shrubs like *Calluna vulgaris* and *Vaccinium spp.* over that of grasses like *Nardus stricta*, *Festuca spp.* and *Agrostis spp.* in these semi-natural mountain grasslands, it seems that grazing by large herbivores can increase nutrient cycling when contrasting functional groups show differential response to herbivory, which adds up to our knowledge of grazing effects on soil processes.

6.3 Plant defoliation recreates observed direct effects of grazing, differences in plant traits are less important

As shown in Chapter 2, large herbivores can affect nutrient cycling and soil microbial properties through their effects on abundance of plant functional group composition with contrasting plant traits, even in low-nutrient ecosystems such as semi-natural mountain grasslands. Could these effects of herbivores on soil properties be explained entirely by plant tissue removal (defoliation), and the subsequent physiological and morphological

6.3 Plant defoliation recreates observed direct effects of grazing, differences in plant traits are less important

changes in plants? I set up a defoliation microcosm experiment with a range of grass species differing in occurrence across productivity gradients (and putatively in functional traits) in order to respond to this question. Thus, in Chapter 3, I set the specific objective of determining the effects of defoliation on soil properties across a range of temperate grass species differing in life-history traits (specific objective 2, see Chapter 1). As plant species showing differential abundance across productivity gradients are well-known to vary in response to different environmental factors, including disturbance such as defoliation (Grime, 1977, 2001), I hypothesised that defoliation effects on soil would be mediated by the different plant species response to defoliation.

Effectively, the microcosm experiment showed that defoliation can consistently recreate those stimulatory effects of grazing on soil processes observed in the field, including N availability and mineralization rates. However, unlike the field experiment, defoliation reduced microbial biomass C and did not affect microbial biomass N. Reduction in microbial biomass C was related to reductions in root biomass, which suggests a strong donor-controlled food web that is characteristic of short-term pot experiments. However, no effects of defoliation on soil microbial N might indicate that defoliation did not mimic effects of grazing on soil microbial community composition (increase in bacteria in relation to fungi), which are reported when grazing stimulates soil nutrient cycling (Bardgett et al., 1998, 2003; Bardgett and Wardle, 2010). On the other hand, increases in N availability were possibly related to reduction in plant root biomass and total root length, which limited plant capacity to take up soil nutrients.

Contrary to my expectations, inter-specific differences in response to defoliation across the grass species were of small or no importance for most soil processes measured. Lack of species effects on soil properties observed in this experiment (Chapter

6.4 Indirect effects of grazing alter plant competition

3) is in contrast to other studies where plant species have been shown to differ in their effects on soil properties (e.g., Innes et al., 2004; Bezemer et al., 2006; Harrison and Bardgett, 2010; Orwin et al., 2010). Since my experiment included a broad variation in life history traits, it is likely that this variation included differences in traits such as grazing response (Pakeman, 2004), litter quality (Niemann et al., 1992), root exudates production (Bais et al., 2006), susceptibility to mycorrhizal infection (Johnson et al., 1997), all of which could be affected by defoliation, and affect soil micro-organisms and the processes driven by them. Therefore, how can these results be reconciled with those in the field study where variation in plant functional traits might explain effects of grazing on soil processes? I suggest that other factors might be more important than inter-specific variation in plant traits in mediating the effects of defoliation on soil processes under the conditions of the microcosm experiment. Namely, the short-term nature of the experiment that might not simulate appropriately long-term effects of grazing, which include replacement of some functional groups by others, and the inclusion of only one functional group (graminoids) might explain why different plant traits were of no importance, although these ideas have yet to be tested.

6.4 Indirect effects of grazing alter plant competition

Direct effects of grazing on plant-plant interactions, particularly competition, have been widely studied in order to understand the non-random plant assemblages, which characterise grazing environments (Louda et al., 1990). However, whether herbivores can indirectly affect plant-plant interactions (an herbivore-plant-soil feedback) through their effects on soil properties, as those described in Chapter 2, is a much less explored topic.

6.4 Indirect effects of grazing alter plant competition

Therefore, in Chapter 4, I assessed how the effects of grazing on soil properties affect competition dynamics in dominant plant species of semi-natural grassland (specific objective 3, see Chapter 1). This was carried out through a microcosm plant competition experiment, which allowed me to separate the intra- and inter-specific components of plant of competition, and included the effect of soil source from the contrasting grazing regimes described in Chapter 2. Selected plant species were *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta*, a sedge and a grass respectively, which exhibit contrasting responses to long-term grazing (*E. vaginatum* is abundant in ungrazed conditions whereas *N. stricta* does in long-term grazed conditions).

Overall, it was found that grazing can exert indirect effects on plant competition through its effects on soils. Thus, the competitive effect of *Nardus stricta* increased twofold when this species was grown in soils from continuously-grazed grasslands where it is dominant. On the other hand, when *Eriophorum vaginatum* (dominant in ungrazed habitats) was grown in soils from the continuously-grazed grasslands, its competitive effect on *N. stricta* was reduced by half. These results are consistent with those found in other studies where grazing effects on soil properties or microbial communities have been shown to affect plant performance (Frank et al., 2003; Sørensen et al., 2008a,b). However, as far as I am concerned, this is the first proof that grazing induced plant-soil feedbacks can affect differentially the components of plant competition (intra- and inter-specific). Differential effects of soil from sources differing in grazing management coincided with both differences in soil properties previously observed in the field study (Chapter 2) and plant traits of the superior competitor (Chapter 3 and Chapter 4). In this way, the grazing-conditioned soil showed higher rates of microbial activity and N availability in comparison with the ungrazed-conditioned soil. These differences in

6.4 Indirect effects of grazing alter plant competition

soil properties between grazed- and ungrazed-conditioned soils might be explained by differences in soil microbial communities or in the quality of soil organic matter between the continuously-grazed and the ungrazed areas. With respect to plant traits, traits of the superior competitor *N. stricta* related to its allocation of biomass into exploitative structures might have contributed to its higher competitive ability in comparison with *E. vaginatum*. Thus, *N. stricta* showed higher proportional biomass in roots, unlike *E. vaginatum* which did in storage structures (crowns). This is consistent with what I observed in Chapter 3, where *N. stricta* capacity to withstand defoliation was strongly related to its high root biomass allocation, and with those findings of Hartley and Amos (1999) where *N. stricta* higher competitive ability in comparison with dwarf-shrubs was associated to its root traits.

Other potential mechanisms by which soil microbes can alter plant-plant interactions include a decrease in plant performance as a result of soil-borne pathogens, and mechanisms related to the role of soil microbes in regulating plant niche overlap and competition for soil resources (Reynolds et al., 2003; Bever et al., 2010). For instance, with respect to soil micro-organisms effects on plant niche overlap, continuous grazing might have affected the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi community, so that plant species might have had differential access to soil nutrients across grazed and ungrazed sites. It is well known that mycorrhizae can increase plant performance under nutrient limiting conditions (Bever et al., 2001), and that sedge species like *E. vaginatum* do not rely on these fungal symbionts (Wein, 1973; Brundrett, 2002). This might have given *N. stricta* a competitive advantage on *E. vaginatum*. Whether changes on soil mycorrhizae and soil microbial communities are related to the competitive balance between upland plant species is something which remains to be clarified.

6.5 Indirect effects of grazing are not explained by soil microbes effects on soil resource competition

I explored into more detail whether the differential effects of herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks observed in Chapter 4 and described above could be caused by soil micro-organisms effects on plant niche overlap of soil resources, namely inorganic N (IN) and organic N (ON). To do this, I set up another microcosms experiment with the specific objective of linking herbivore-plant-soil feedbacks effects on plant competition to effects of soil microbes on N uptake preferences of *E. vaginatum* and *N. stricta* (specific objective 4, see Chapter 1). This experiment included the use of stable ^{13}C and ^{15}N isotopes in a plant competition experiment. I hypothesised that microbial communities from areas subjected to contrasting grazing regimes would affect plant competition for organic and inorganic N. I based this hypothesis on previous results of grazing-induced feedbacks on plant competition (Chapter 4, see above), and because microbial communities differing in activity or composition (as those between continuously-grazed and ungrazed areas, Chapter 2 and Chapter 4) could alter plant N competition by modifying N cycling.

In contrast to my hypothesis, N competition between *N. stricta* and *E. vaginatum* was not explained by different microbial communities associated with different grazing regimes. Lack of effects of microbial communities that differed in activity on plant N uptake preferences is in contrast to results of a previous study which showed that the stimulation of microbial activity led to changes on plant N uptake preferences (Dunn et al., 2006). Soil microbial biomass C and N measured at the end of the plant competition experiment (Chapter 5) were much lower than those found in the field (Chapter 2), and than those observed in the microcosm experiment where herbivore-plant soil

6.6 Ecological and management implications

feedbacks affected plant competition (Chapter 4). These difference in soil microbial properties among the experiments, and the fact that I did not measure the fraction of N taken-up by soil microbes in the N-competition experiment, make it difficult to interpret whether soil microbes from soil with different grazing management were functionally equivalent (Wertz et al., 2006, 2007), or whether the lack of effect was due to a small size of the microbial community. Studies testing effects of microbial communities on N uptake patterns and plant competition for N are scarce. Therefore, more research on this topic would shed light on how soil microbial composition can affect plant niche overlap, and thus plant species competition and coexistence.

As mentioned above, it is likely that *N. stricta* out-competed *E. vaginatum* in grazed-conditioned soils more easily based on its root traits and the higher activity of microbial communities to mineralize N in these soils. Other plant trait potentially related to higher competitive ability unexplored so far might be the capacity to modify preferences of IN and ON uptake in competitors, as *N. stricta* did on *E. vaginatum*. This N uptake preference change caused by *N. stricta* on *E. vaginatum* is likely to have increased N niche overlap in these plant species, with potential implications for mechanisms by which these species coexist in semi-natural mountain ecosystems, and which are discussed next.

6.6 Ecological and management implications

What are the ecological and applied implications of the results observed in this thesis? On one side, taken cautiously, my results (Chapter 2) have implications on total soil C and N storage policies and land use management in upland ecosystems. Since these systems are among the major reservoirs of C on terrestrial ecosystems (Milne and Brown,

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1997), attention is being devoted to understanding the regulation of C dynamics as C sequestration in organic soils as an important ecosystem service (Dominati et al., 2010) delivered by these areas. The grazed grassland had higher rates of nutrient cycling (higher N mineralization rates), and microbial activity, suggesting that grazing could lead to higher decomposition rates and less C sequestration in soils. Nevertheless, this was not the case, and the continuously-grazed grassland had similar total soil C values as those in the ungrazed area. This agrees with results found in other studies in nutrient-poor semi-natural mountain ecosystems showing that long-term grazing exclusion does not lead to increases in total soil C, at least in the superficial organic soil horizons (Garnett et al., 2000; Ward et al., 2007, but see Bardgett et al. 2001). Therefore, grazing as a land use activity could be compatible with soil C sequestration in these ecosystems. However, more extensive sampling and experimental studies varying grazing intensity are necessary to prove this assertion. Interestingly, it has been shown recently that grazing can increase the temperature sensitivity of soil C in the rich-organic soils of semi-natural mountain areas (Paz-Ferreiro et al. *in preparation*). This last finding suggests that grazing could interact with climate warming to effectively increase soil respiration in these ecosystems. Additionally, whereas grazing cessation might not increase soil C in the order of a few decades, grazing cessation is still associated with an increase in the size of the litter horizon, whose loss under grazing by livestock represents a considerable C loss (Ward et al., 2007).

My results also have implications for understanding the mechanisms that determine plant species coexistence across gradients of grazing intensity and soil properties in temperate semi-natural mountain grasslands (Chapter 4 and Chapter 5). *Nardus stricta* and *E. vaginatum* have marked differences in their ecological optima across the gradients

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in grazing intensity and soil properties (particularly moisture), which characterise semi-natural mountain grasslands. Whereas *E. vaginatum* occurs preferentially in areas with higher soil moisture (Edgell, 1971; Wein, 1973), *N. stricta* tends to dominate in long-term grazed areas. Higher occurrence of *N. stricta* in long-term grazed conditions is thought to result from the avoidance of this species by herbivores (Welch, 1986) caused by its low palatability as a result of high contents of silica in leaves (Massey et al., 2007, , although note that less selective herbivores such as cattle can graze heavily on it, and that my results in Chapter 3 suggest that *N. stricta* also exhibits tolerance). Despite their different ecological optima, these two plant species coexist along the gradients in grazing and soil moisture content occurring in different pairwise densities (Chadwick, 1960; Wein, 1973; Rodwell, 1992)). My results on plant competition in Chapter 4 and 5 showed that *N. stricta* is the superior competitor, at least in the conditions tested in the microcosm experiments. Combined, this higher competitive ability of *N. stricta*, the strong positive soil-feedback present in this species in grazed-conditioned soils (Chapter 4), and the higher niche overlap in N uptake preferences when both species competed (Chapter 5), suggest that mechanisms different to those based on niche complementarity must operate in order for these plant species to coexist in areas where they co-occur. These other coexistence mechanisms might be related to those generating spatial heterogeneity (i.e. in soil conditions such as moisture), and/or those that promote non-equilibrium species densities (i.e. gap creation by herbivores) which reduce competitive exclusion of *E. vaginatum*.

6.7 Conclusions

Throughout this work, it has been shown that large herbivores can exert important direct and indirect effects on ecosystems processes, likely by changing the abundance of different plant functional groups with contrasting functional traits, and the concomitant changes in soil microbes and other components of the soil food web. Overall, my results showed that grazing management can have important consequences for soil nutrient dynamics and soil microbial properties in upland ecosystems. In particular, grazing increases N mineralization and microbial activity (Chapter 2), and plant defoliation can consistently recreate these stimulatory effects of grazing on soil N cycling in nutrient-poor soils (Chapter 2, Chapter 3), despite the fact that plant traits within a functional group (graminoids) are weakly related to defoliation effects on soil properties (Chapter 3). Additionally, effects of grazing on soil can alter plant competition outcome of selected dominant plant species differing in their response to long-term grazing (Chapter 4). However, these indirect effects of grazing on plant competition are not explained by how different microbial communities affect preferences of inorganic or organic N uptake in these dominant plant species (Chapter 5), but by species-specific traits related to competition for soil resources and grazing effects on microbes, which increase N availability (Chapter 4 and Chapter 5). Overall, my results show the importance of ungulate herbivores to increase rates of nutrient cycling in poor-nutrient semi-natural mountain grasslands and their indirect role regulating plant-plant interactions. My results also suggest that mechanisms different to resource complementarity can be involved in the coexistence of plant species and highlight potential trade-offs associated with herbivory by domestic ungulates in the provision of ecosystem services such as C storage.

Appendix A

Figure A.1: Principal component analysis based on the correlation matrix of transformed plant variables (shoot biomass, root biomass, root length and root:shoot ratio). The first and second eigenvalues explained 78 and 20 % of the variance respectively. The Box-plots indicate data distribution. Top, sampling units identified by defoliation treatment. Bottom, sampling units identified by species. PC1 = first principal component, PC2 = second principal component. Nardus = *N. stricta*, Festuca = *F. rubra*, Poa = *P. pratensis*, Holcus = *H. lanatus*, Anthoxanthum = *A. odoratum*, Agrostis = *A. capillaris*, Lolium = *L. perenne*. CN = control, MC = two-weekly defoliation, HC = one-weekly defoliation -

Appendix B

Figure B.1: Indirect effects of grazing and direct effects of density of heterospecifics on: a) total shoot biomass, b) crown biomass, c) root biomass of *Eriophorum vaginatum* (Ev) and *Nardus stricta* (Ns). Plants were grown in a glasshouse microcosm experiment with soil coming from a grazed *Nardus*-dominated acidic upland grassland (G⁺) or an *Eriophorum*-dominated ungrazed area (G⁻) in the Yorkshire Dales, England. *E. vaginatum* plants grew in a range of densities of *N. stricta* shown in the horizontal axis. *N. stricta* plants grew in a range of densities of *E. vaginatum*. -

Appendix C

C.1 Research products

As a result of this work the next research products were completed:

C.1.1 Papers in journals in the science citation index:

- Medina-Roldán, E., and R.D. Bardgett. 2011. Plant and soil responses to defoliation: a comparative study of grass species with contrasting life history strategies. *Plant and Soil* 344:377-388.
- Medina-Roldán, E., J. Paz-Ferreiro, and R.D. Bardgett. Influence of re-wilding practices versus sheep grazing on aboveground and belowground properties of upland grasslands. *Ecosystems, Agriculture, and Environment*. (*in review*).
- Medina-Roldán, E., J. Paz-Ferreiro, and R.D. Bardgett. Grazing-induced effects on soil properties modify plant competitive interactions in semi-natural mountain grassland. *Oecologia*. (*in review*).

C.1.2 Posters:

- Medina-Roldán, E. and R.D. Bardgett. Soil and plant responses to defoliation among temperate grasses differing in relative growth rates. British Ecological Society Annual Meeting. Hertfordshire, UK. September, 2009.
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